

Marine heatwaves and the phytoplankton spring bloom

A comparative survey of marine heatwaves, spring bloom events
and their relationship in the North Sea and Baltic Sea

Master Thesis

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20.12.2019

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Berlin, den 20.12.2019

Henrike Lorenz

Acknowledgment

I would like to thank my supervisors Dr. Jürgen Fischer and Dr. Hans-Peter Grossart for giving me the opportunity to work on this topic. For further academic advise and support I need to thank Dr. Bronwyn Cahill and Dr. Igor Ogashawara. I would also like to thank Benjamin Schumacher from BSH for providing me with the SST data.

Finally I am thankful to the people proof reading this thesis and to my friends and flatmates for baring with me during the time of writing. A special thanks goes to Emmy for providing me with dinner on so many occasions and to Anita for working next to me whenever possible.

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Zusammenfassung

Der Klimawandel hat auch in marinen Ökosystemen schwerwiegende Folgen. Eine dieser Folgen ist die Zunahme der Frequenz und Dauer extremer Hitzeereignisse, so genannter Mariner Hitzewellen (MHW) (Oliver et al., 2018). Für die Nordsee und Ostsee wurde das Vorkommen von MHW bis jetzt nicht untersucht. Diese können einen schädlichen Einfluss auf Spezies, Ökosysteme und ökosystemare Prozesse haben (Smale et al., 2019). Zum Einfluss von MHW auf Phytoplankton gibt es bis jetzt jedoch nur wenig Forschung. Ziel dieser Arbeit war es, zu zeigen, dass Temperatur und insbesondere MHW einen relevanten Einfluss auf die Phytoplankton Frühjahresblüte haben. Es sollte insbesondere heraus gefunden werden, ob es eine Beziehung zwischen parallel stattfindenden MHW und Blüteevents gibt. Außerdem sollten die Eigenschaften und Entwicklungen von MHW und Frühjahrsblüten in der Ostsee und Nordsee beschrieben werden. Dafür wurden Tagesraster aus der Satelliten-Fernerkundung für Meeresoberflächentemperatur (SST), Wolkenbedeckung (TCC), Windgeschwindigkeit und Chlorophyll a (chl-a) akquiriert. Aus ihnen wurden Zeitreihen aus Tagesmitteln für zwanzig Seeregionen erstellt. Es wurden Korrelationen zwischen den Monatsmitteln von chl-a und jeweils SST, Windgeschwindigkeit und TCC berechnet und verglichen. MHW wurden mit einer Grenzwertmethode nach Hobday et al. (2016, 2018) erfasst und kategorisiert. Die Frühjahresblüten wurden ebenfalls mit Hilfe einer Grenzwertmethode identifiziert. Für Blüteevents und MHW wurden Eventindices berechnet. Für diese Indices wurde der Mann-Kendall-Test durchgeführt, um auf mögliche Trends zu testen. Abschließend wurde Spearmans Korrelationskoeffizient für MHW- und Blüte-Indices für zwei Fälle berechnet: 1. Für Blüten und MHW, die bis zu einem Monat vor dem Blüteevent statt gefunden hatten. 2. Für Blüten und MHW, die gleichzeitig statt gefunden hatten.

Es konnte gezeigt werden, dass SST im Gegensatz zu den anderen beiden Parametern (TCC und Windgeschwindigkeit) eine komplexere Beziehung zu chl-a hat. MHW und Blüteevents konnten erfolgreich identifiziert werden. Die Arbeit gibt einen umfangreichen Überblick über ihre Eigenschaften, Entwicklungen sowie räumliche und zeitliche Verteilungen. Es wurden positive, signifikante Trends für SST und die Frequenz von MHW in beiden Meeren und den Beginn der Frühjahrsblüte in der Ostsee festgestellt. Es wurde gezeigt, dass in der Ostsee zwar mehr und intensivere MHW auftreten, die Nordsee aber stärker von MHW höherer Kategorien betroffen ist. Im Frühjahr wurde ein Tiefpunkt in der Frequenz und Intensität von MHW für beide Meere festgestellt. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass es bei gleichzeitig auftretenden MHW und Blüten eine positive Beziehung zwischen der Dauer und Intensität der MHW und dem Ausmaß der Blüte gibt.

Abbreviations

AVHRR	Advanced Very-High-Resolution Radiometer
BaS	Baltic Sea
BSH	Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency of Germany (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie)
chl-a	Chlorophyll a
CDOM	Colored dissolved organic matter
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DOY	Day of year
DWD	German Meteorological Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst)
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ENSO	El Niño–Southern Oscillation
ESA	European Space Agency
ERA	European Reanalysis
HAB	Harmful algal blooms
I _{mean}	Mean intensity
I _{max}	Maximum intensity
IOD	Indian Ocean Dipole
IOP	Inherent optical properties
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
OC-CCI	Ocean Colour – Climate Change Initiative
OCI	Ocean Colour Imager
OCRS	Ocean colour remote sensing
MERIS	Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
Metop	Meteorological Operational Satellite
MHW	Marine heatwaves
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NA	Not available
n.d.	not dated
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NoS	North Sea

SeaWiFS	Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
SPM	Suspended particulate matter
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
T	Temperature
TCC	Total cloud cover
Wdspd	Wind speed
VIIRS	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite

1 Introduction

Media coverage of catastrophic events like huge wild fires, floods and heat spells has become an almost weekly affair. It is now widely known that anthropogenic climate change is not only accompanied by changes in climatic means but also by changes in the patterns of extreme events. Such events may cause serious ecological and economical damage in a relatively short period of time. The IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) report (2014) defines an extreme event as an event as rare as the 10th or 90th percentile of its distribution (Fig. 1b). It can be described by applying event indices like frequency, maximum or lengths. There is strong evidence for a decrease in extreme cold events and an increase in heavy precipitation, heatwaves, droughts and tropical cyclones in the North Atlantic (Fig 1a) (IPCC, 2014).

Figure 1: a: Types of extreme events that have changed their patterns. Upward arrows signify an increase, downward arrows a decrease. b: Shift of the temperature anomaly probability function between 1951-1980 (blue line) and 1981-2010 (red line). The red and blue areas signify the hottest and coldest 10% (extreme temperature events). The shift towards a warmer climate increased the number of extreme hot days. Taken from IPCC (2014).

In the field of ecology, extreme events have gained more and more attention in recent years. So far, the focus has been mainly terrestrial but the occurrence of massive oceanic heat phenomena during

the last decade have drawn attention to extreme heat events in the marine environment. They are called marine heatwaves (MHW).

After studying the heatwave in 2011 at the Australian west coast and finding significant changes in biodiversity patterns and community structures Wernberg et al. (2013) claimed that „the frequency, magnitude and geographical extent of extreme events needs to be considered in conjunction with mean warming trends for accurate prediction and mitigation of climate change effects on marine ecosystems.” Fraser et al. (2014) who studied the effect of the same MHW and who found drastic changes in the local sea grass community stated: “Extreme climatic events will dictate the response of ecosystems to climate change, yet are under-studied in marine ecosystems. The interaction of stressors from such events has the potential to amplify negative impacts and drive ecosystems into alternate states.” Following up on these studies the Marine Heatwaves international working group was formed in 2014. They proposed a definition and detection method of MHW (Hobday et al., 2016) and performed first surveys concerned with the distribution and properties of MHW (Holbrook et al., 2019) and their ecological consequences (Smale et al., 2019). Notable MHW and important drivers are presented in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Notable marine heatwaves and important drivers. Taken from Oliver (2018).

When studying the consequences of MHW the focus so far has been mainly on animals, multi cellular plants and ecosystem functions. Yet, phytoplankton, the microbial photo-synthetic active organisms living in marine and fresh water bodies, are clearly effected by climate change as well (Guinder and Molinero, 2013). Phytoplankton are the base of the marine food web, accountable for half of the global primary production and a sink for carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Guinder & Molinero,

2013; Longhurst et al., 1995). The most important event in phytoplankton phenology is the spring bloom, the abrupt growth of phytoplankton populations when light and temperature increase at the beginning of the year (Williams and Follows, 2011).

Temporal shifts of spring bloom events have been documented and so have shifts in geographic distribution and species patterns of phytoplankton communities. These changes are associated with consequences of climate change like rising water temperatures or increasing acidification due to higher CO₂ levels in the atmosphere (Guinder and Molinero, 2013). Nonetheless, the impacts of climate change on phytoplankton are still debated (Boyce, Lewis, and Worm, 2010; McQuatters-Gollop et al., 2011) and the mechanisms are not fully understood.

These changes do not just impact phytoplankton in the open oceans but in marginal seas and coastal waters as well. Here, effects are often enhanced by the strong anthropogenic influence from adjacent coasts (Ciglenečki et al., 2015). During past decades several regime shifts in phytoplankton species composition have been documented in two marginal seas of northern Europe: the North Sea (NoS) and the Baltic Sea (BaS) (IOW, 2012; M. Scharfe et al., 2008). Additionally, shifts in the beginning of the spring bloom event, its peak and its length have been reported for BaS regions (Kahru, Elmgren, & Savchuk, 2016). These changes might be connected to changing temperatures but the analysis is difficult: Phytoplankton are impacted by a complex set of parameters like light, nutrient concentration, water body stratification, wind forcing, predators and pH-levels (Guinder and Molinero, 2013). Temperature is just one of them and, to complicate the situation further, is connected with other parameters like stratification or zooplankton activity.

Research has shown that bloom events can have a positive effect on the sea surface heat budget (e.g. Kahru, Leppanen, and Rud, 1993). In return, this can favor bloom growth, thus leading to a feedback scenario (Dickey and Falkowski, 2005). This raises the question if MHW might have an effect on phytoplankton blooms or vice versa.

Most of the studies on the effect of high temperatures on phytoplankton apply mesocosm experiments (e.g. Remy, Hillebrand, & Flöder, 2017; Seifert, Weithoff, & Vos, 2015; Stefanidou et al., 2018). These experiments are limited to a defined amount of time, space and parameters. While they do offer insight into the processes of the marine environment they cannot fully represent the complex real-world situation. The green pigment of phytoplankton, chlorophyll, can be detected via remote sensing by airborne sensors or satellites. Most common is the sensing of chlorophyll a (chl-a), a special form of the pigment (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014). Such remotely sensed images can be used to derive chlorophyll concentrations which work as a proxy for phytoplankton

concentrations. Sea surface temperature (SST) can be remotely sensed as well via satellite microwave radiometers or infrared radiometers. Thus, remotely-sensed images provide data over long time periods on a global level and may offer new insight on the relationship of phytoplankton bloom events and high temperatures.

The aim of this thesis is to show that SST and MHW are meaningful parameters for the phytoplankton spring bloom and to find out if there is a relationship between co-occurring MHW and bloom events. It also aims to describe properties and changes of MHW and spring bloom events in the NoS and BaS. So far, MHW have not been studied in either seas. To achieve this, time series derived from remote sensing images are applied.

The following research questions were formulated:

1. How does the relationship of chl-a and SST compare to other meteorological parameters?
2. What are the properties of the phytoplankton spring bloom in the NoS and the BaS? Did they change during the last 20 years?
3. Do MHW occur in the NoS and BaS? Are there changes in their frequency, duration and intensity during the last 30 years?
4. Is there a relationship between co-occurring MHW and spring bloom events?

To answer these questions, daily raster data of SST, chl-a concentrations, total cloud coverage (TCC) and wind speed were obtained. Monthly correlations between chl-a and respectively SST, TCC and wind speed were calculated and compared. Using the SST data, MHW were detected and categorized. Spring bloom events were detected using a the chl-a data. For the detection of both events (MHW and blooms) a threshold method was applied. A threshold was defined and whenever a parameter exceeded this threshold for a certain amount of time this was registered as an event. Subsequently, event indices were calculated for MHW and blooms. Trends in SST and event indices were analyzed using the Mann-Kendall trend test. Finally Spearman's correlation was calculated for event indices of co-occurring MHW and bloom events.

In the following chapter (Sec 2) the state of the art regarding the research on MHW, phytoplankton during climate change and the remote sensing of phytoplankton is presented. Section 3 offers a summary of the geography and phytoplankton biology in the study region, namely the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. The methods used in this work are described in Sec 4 and the derived results in Sec 5. The research questions are answered in the discussion in Sec 6. The thesis is concluded with a summary and an outlook in Sec 7.

2 State of the Art

This chapter gives an overview on prevailing theories on extreme events and introduces MHW as a form of extreme event. The definition of MHW is presented as well as mechanisms, trends and ecological effects. An overview on the ecological meaning of phytoplankton and its blooms is given and the role of phytoplankton during climate change is outlined. A special focus is put on its relationship with rising temperatures. Finally ocean color remote sensing is introduced and common methods to measure chl-a concentrations and detected bloom events are explained.

2.1 Marine heatwaves as a form of extreme events

2.1.1 Extreme climatic events in ecology

A climatic extreme event, for example a drought, a heatwave or extreme rainfall, is defined as an event that is as rare as the 10th or 90th percentile of its probability function. It can be described using event indices like the magnitude, frequency and duration (IPCC, 2014).

Smith (2011) pointed out that this definition might be too narrow from an ecologist's point of view. Smith proposes that not only the statistical rareness of the event should be considered but the degree of the ecological response as well. Smith defines an extreme climatic event as “[...] an episode or occurrence in which a statistically rare or unusual climatic period alters ecosystem structure and/or function well outside the bounds of what is considered typical or normal variability.”

Extreme events can have severe impacts on species, populations and ecosystems. Their ecological consequences include effects on morphology (e.g. shape, size or color of individuals), effects on behavior and reproduction (e.g. timing of breeding), effects on population and community dynamics (e.g. population booms and crashes) and effects at the ecosystem level (e.g. changes in species composition and diversity) (Parmesan, Root, and Willig, 2000; Smith, 2011).

Jentsch & Beierkuhnlein (2008) stated that the ecological effects of extreme events might even be stronger than those following the changes in mean conditions. But Harris et al. (2018) proposed that it is actually the combination of long-term changes of climatological means and extreme events that trigger grave ecosystem responses. They conclude, using a “press and pulse” framework, that the

impact of the extreme event (the pulse) also depend on the state of the climatological means (the press).

While broad research on the impact of extreme events on terrestrial ecosystems exist for decades the topic of such events in the marine environment is fairly new. In recent years extreme warming events of the ocean, so called MHW have gained scientific attention.

2.1.2 Marine heatwaves

In the early years only very prominent MHW (for example 2003 Mediterranean Sea, 2011 Western Australia and 2013-2015 Pacific Northwest of USA and Canada, see Fig. 2) with strong and easy to measure effects on ecosystems have been studied (Fraser et al., 2014; Garrabou et al., 2009; Wernberg et al., 2016; Wernberg et al., 2013) but a general understanding on the mechanics of MHW and their global distribution is lacking. In 2016, Hobday et al. (2016) were the first to introduce a consistent definition of MHW and a method to detect them. They pointed out that a clear definition is necessary to compare MHW and to understand their mechanics and consequences. Based on the IPCC's definition for extreme temperature events in the atmosphere they proposed the following: "We generally define an MHW as a prolonged, discrete anomalously warm water event that can be described by its duration, intensity, rate of evolution, and spatial extent. Specifically, we consider an anomalously warm event to be an MHW if it lasts for five or more days, with temperatures warmer than the 90th percentile based on a 30-year historical baseline period." (It has to be noted that an MHW can occur in any season, even in winter.)

Two years later, this approach was extended by the introduction of a classification scheme and a naming convention for MHW. This allowed for the classification of MHW "based on the degree to which temperatures exceed the local climatology" into four categories ranging from "moderate" to "extreme" (Hobday et al., 2018). These works accelerated the MHW research and resulted in further publications on the topic (among others: Frölicher & Laufkötter, 2018; Harris et al., 2018; Holbrook et al., 2019; Oliver et al., 2018).

Trends in MHW

Using Hobday and others (2016) MHW framework, Oliver et al. (2018) and Holbrook et al. (2019) found that MHW events are heterogeneously distributed across the globe. Oliver et al. (2018) also found a significant increase of MHW days and duration during the last century (see Fig. 3).

Between 1926 and 2016, the average MHW frequency increased by 34% while average MHW duration increased by 17%. Since 1982 0.45 more events as well as 1.3 more MHW days per decade were measured. There also seems to be a weak, positive but so far insignificant trend regarding MHW intensity. As can be seen in Fig. 3, the changes in frequency are correlated with the increase of sea surface temperature (SST). It is concluded that, due to anthropogenic climate change, a further increase in MHW can be expected (Oliver et al., 2018).

Figure 3: Global pattern and changes of MHW event indices and mean SST. a,c,f & g show mean of MHW frequency, MHW intensity, MHW duration and mean SST over the 1982-2016 period; b,d,f & h show difference between the 1982-1998 and 2000-2016 periods for these four parameters. Hatching indicates significant changes ($p < 0.05$). Taken from Oliver et al. (2018).

Mechanisms of MHW

Next to changes in mean temperature, MHW “may be caused by the interaction of many local and remote processes and phenomena acting across a large range of temporal and spatial scales” (Holbrook et al., 2019). Frölicher & Laufkötter (2018) point out as well that MHW can be caused by oceanic and atmospheric forcing and that location and season play a role in MHW formation. As can be seen in Fig. 4, MHW drivers range from local and short-time phenomena like air-sea heat fluxes and wind-forcing, to global and long-term phenomena like climate oscillations (e.g. El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) or Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD)) and climate change. Many investigated regions display significant changes during specific phases of climate oscillations. Especially ENSO has been identified as a useful predictor for MHW (Holbrook et al., 2019). On the other hand MHW may also influence the development of extreme weather events over land (Frölicher and Laufkötter, 2018).

Figure 4: Space and time scales of characteristic MHW drivers. Taken from Holbrook et al. (2019).

Ecological effects of MHW

MHW cause a variety of effects on marine environments. Smale et al. (2019) investigated eight prominent MHW and found that all of them had negative impacts on species, ecosystems and biological processes. Those impacts included, among others, geographical shifts, reduction or mass mortality of species, changes in biodiversity patterns, harmful algal blooms (HAB), mass strandings of mammals and mass coral bleaching.

Such incidents may be followed by economic consequences like changes in fishing practices and price collapses in the fishing industry (Frölicher and Laufkötter, 2018; Smale et al., 2019).

Besides the mentioning of HAB, phytoplankton are not discussed in the previously quoted works. Up to now, phytoplankton are barely considered in the field of MHW research. And even though the rise of mean temperature is an important topic in phytoplankton ecology, the impact of MHW remains a research gap, which will be shown in the next chapter.

2.2 Phytoplankton and climate change

2.2.1 Definition and meaning of phytoplankton and blooms

Phytoplankton are autotrophic microorganisms that live in oceans, seas and freshwater basins and obtain their energy through photosynthesis. In marine environments, they are the dominant primary producer and therefore the base of the food chain (Guinder and Molinero, 2013; Williams and Follows, 2011). They provide about 50% (~ 50 Gt C/year) of the global primary production which makes them a key player in the global biogeochemical cycle (Field, 1998; Longhurst et al., 1995). They also impact sea-air-energy fluxes and are an important part of the carbon cycle as they export carbon from the euphotic (sunlit) zone to the deep ocean, thus, being a critical driver in the climate system (Guinder and Molinero, 2013).

Phytoplankton depend on light, nutrients and temperature. Their growth and decline is influenced by various processes like stratifying and mixing of the water column, coastal upwelling, wind-forcing, zooplankton grazing or anthropogenic nutrient input, to just name a few (Guinder and Molinero, 2013). Marine phytoplankton communities have a distinct phenology, which follows the annual course of temperature and light. The most important event in the phytoplankton year is the spring bloom, especially in sub polar latitudes (Williams and Follows, 2011). According to

Blondeau-Patissier et al. (2014) a bloom is a “biological event composed of micro-algal species that is sustained both over time and space and that results in noticeable changes in satellite radiance at wavelengths used for algal bloom proxies due to an increase in biomass (in comparison to surrounding algal bloom-free waters)”. In late winter and spring, there is an increase in light and temperature. This increase and the abundance of nutrients in the upper ocean layers brought up by winter mixing of the water body triggers a rapid growth of phytoplankton, causing an event that is known as a spring bloom. It fuels the biochemical processes in the marine ecosystem for the rest of the year and is the “starting shot” for the reproduction of many species which feed on phytoplankton or their predators. Further increase of temperature onsets water column stratification which, on the one hand, inhibits vertical mixing and helps plankton to stay in the euphotic zone but, on the other hand, sets an end to nutrient supply from deeper ocean layers. Subsequently, nutrient depletion and zooplankton grazing cause the end of the bloom in the course of spring. Many marine regions witness a second, weaker bloom in summer or autumn, when, due to cooler temperatures, water stratification is resolved and nutrients are again supplied to the euphotic layer (Guinder and Molinero, 2013; Williams and Follows, 2011; Winder and Sommer, 2012)

Changes in the timing, magnitude and species composition of blooms serve as a good indicator for environmental changes since phytoplankton are very sensitive to altered conditions and tend to respond rapidly. Blooms therefore play a key role in studying the effects of climate change on phytoplankton and marine ecosystems (Edwards, 2016; Racault et al., 2015).

2.2.2 Impacts of climate change on phytoplankton

The general fate of phytoplankton during climate change is still debated. Boyce et al. (2010) found that there was a global decline of about 1% of the global median per year which was contradicted by McQuatters-Gollop et al. (2011) who found there was actually an increase in global phytoplankton concentrations. A final answer on this issue is still anticipated.

Nonetheless, it has been shown many times that phytoplankton is effected by climate change in various ways. Guinder & Molinero (2013) summarize the six most important responses:

1. Negative trends of growth and photosynthesis of calcifying phytoplankton due to rising levels of CO₂ which have led to an acidification of the oceans.
2. Changes in species patterns, beneficial to smaller species, due to increased stratification caused by rising temperatures.
3. Changes in timing, magnitude and species composition of the spring bloom.

4. Increase of HAB in coastal systems and mini-blooms outside of spring.
5. Changes in molecular composition and quality of nutrients due to increased CO₂.
6. Nutrient level decrease in the euphotic layer caused by earlier and longer stratification.

These responses may be succeeded by further consequences for marine ecosystems like changes in the light regime, negative impacts on the biological carbon pump (Basu and Mackey, 2018) and decoupling of zooplankton grazing activities (Winder and Sommer, 2012). The latter can in turn affect the whole food chain.

2.2.3 Relationships of phytoplankton and high temperatures

Next to rising CO₂-levels, the global temperature increase is one of the main interests when studying the impact of climate change on phytoplankton. During recent years, a variety of experiments and studies regarding this matter have been carried out. Most of them are mesocosm experiments (medium-sized experiments in a limited body of water with close to natural conditions) which treat a sample of phytoplankton species with different levels of temperature. The results of these experiments show loss of species (Remy, Hillebrand, and Flöder, 2017; Seifert, Weithoff, and Vos, 2015; Stefanidou et al., 2018), decrease in biomass (Remy, Hillebrand, and Flöder, 2017; Sommer and Lengfellner, 2008; Sommer and Lewandowska, 2011; Stefanidou et al., 2018), decrease in cell size (Sommer and Lengfellner, 2008; Sommer and Lewandowska, 2011), dominance of smaller species (Remy, Hillebrand, and Flöder, 2017) and acceleration of the bloom peak (Sommer and Lengfellner, 2008; Sommer and Lewandowska, 2011) in high temperature treatments.

While many of these experiments alter additional factors like salinity (Stefanidou et al., 2018), turbidity (Remy, Hillebrand, and Flöder, 2017) or zooplankton grazing pressure (Sommer and Lewandowska, 2011), they cannot reproduce the complex conditions in a real-life scenario. Studies which evaluate in situ measurements of phytoplankton after a natural MHW might allow a more realistic view on the matter but only few of them exist (e.g. Du & Peterson, 2018). However, such studies can only show the effects of a particular MHW in a particular region and one should be careful to draw general conclusions.

While phytoplankton blooms may be influenced by changes in temperature, it has in return an influence on the upper ocean heat budget, which, again, might lead to feedback on the bloom. Since phytoplankton absorbs visible radiation it can cause changes in the upper ocean heat budget, depending on the concentration and vertical distribution of chlorophyll (Dickey & Falkowski,

2005).

It has been shown in various experiments that an increase of phytoplankton in the euphotic zone can positively effect the rate of heating of the zone, thus increasing the temperature and can eventually lead to a smaller depth of the mixed layer (e.g. Lewis, Cullen, & Platt, 1983; Lewis, Kuring, & Yentsch, 1988; Stramska & Dickey, 1993). Kahru, Leppanen, and Rud (1993) found that blooms of cyanobacteria in the BaS can lead to an increase in SST by up to 0.5°C. Experiments done with climate models have supported these results. Timmermann & Jin (2002) used a coupled atmosphere-ocean model to show that phytoplankton blooms increased warming in upper ocean layers in the Pacific and consequently have an influence on the amplitude and timing of ENSO. Wetzel et al. (2006) investigated the influence of phytoplankton on the global climate cycle using a fully couple climate model and came to the conclusion that “ the influence of marine biology on the radiative budget of the upper ocean should be considered in detailed simulations of the earth’s climate”. They found that influence of phytoplankton blooms on the upper ocean heat budget is especially strong in the Northern hemisphere. For instance, they found evidence that the earlier start of the spring warming is linked to the influence of the phytoplankton spring bloom on the upper surface heating.

2.3 Detecting phytoplankton blooms using remote sensing

2.3.1 Ocean colour remote sensing

As has been pointed out in the previous chapter, there are still many open questions regarding the path of phytoplankton during climate change. While mesocosm experiments and in situ measure-ments help to understand the mechanisms that fuel phytoplankton reactions to climate change, they a) fail to reflect the complex real-life processes on large spatial or temporal scales and b) are time and work intensive. Remote sensing of ocean colour, however, can provide a cost effective, spatially and temporally synoptic view of the ocean (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014).

Ocean colour remote sensing (OCRS) utilizes satellite or airborne measurements of the spectral reflectance of the sea surface to retrieve the inherent optical properties (IOP), meaning the absorption and scattering properties of the water body (IOCCG, 2004). The substances influencing

the IOPs are the ocean water, phytoplankton, colored dissolved organic matter (CDOM), suspended particulate matter (SPM) and water bubbles (Mobley, 2010).

There is a strong focus on phytoplankton in publications concerned with OCSRS. The proxy of phytoplankton concentration is the concentration of chlorophyll a (chl-a), the green pigment of the algae which absorbs the energy that is needed for photosynthesis. It has a distinct spectral signature, with high absorption in the blue and the red (see Fig. 5) and high reflectance in the green part of the visible spectrum. Thus, it is relatively easy to discriminate from other water constituents.

Figure 5: Absorption signature of chl-a in the visible part of the spectrum. Taken from Schirber (2013).

A variety of algorithms exist to detect and measure chl-a. Reflectance band-ratio algorithms which make use of the reflectance difference in the blue and green part of the spectrum and calculate spectral band-ratios are most common. A simpler approach are reflectance classification algorithms which use only one band and are therefore not very reliable, especially in coastal areas (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Pitarch et al., 2016). Spectral band difference algorithms, also known as ocean colour indices like fluorescence line height (FLH), use a baseline subtraction method to detect reflectance peak heights (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2017). Among the more complex methods are neural networks which use machine learning methods and rely on training data sets (Pitarch et al., 2016).

Most of these algorithms work well in open ocean regions, so called case 1 waters, which are dominated by phytoplankton. Blue-green algorithms are effective in these waters as the chlorophyll reflectance signature is rarely disturbed by reflectance of other water constituents. But in the

optically complex case 2 waters, which occur mainly near the shore, measuring chl-a concentrations is still difficult (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Gower and King, 2012; Xing et al., 2007)

. In case 2 waters, aerosols, foam, sun glint, contrails, bottom reflection or high concentrations of suspended matter can mask the chl-a reflectance. And even under ideal conditions, the phytoplankton might not be dominant in the upper ocean layers but in the submerged layers which cannot be observed via remote sensing. Additionally, strong blooms may cause thick floating algal layers which are difficult to assess (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Peters et al., 2005). All these reasons can lead to wrong estimations of chl-a.

In the past two decades, several satellite sensors like SeaWiFS, MODIS and MERIS have been especially designed to measure the optical properties of the ocean. While investigating long time periods, problems often arise when data from different sensors are used. Differences in the position and width of the spectral bands or the spatial resolution lead to differences in the derived chl-a concentration. To address this problem, the Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative (OC-CCI) of the European Space Agency (ESA) publishes a regularly updated chl-a data series with data going back to 1997. It is composed of data from several sensors using different kinds of algorithms (see Sec 4.1.1).

2.3.2 Bloom detection

Platt & Sathyendranath (2008) suggest ecosystem indicators as a tool to monitor changes in phytoplankton ecology. They propose that chl-a concentrations derived from OCSRS can be used for three types of ecosystem indicators:

1. indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton biomass.
2. indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton production.
3. indicators describing changes in community structure.

The first and second type are concerned with the timing and magnitude of blooms and use event indices like maximum amplitude (peak), the time of initiation and termination, the time of the peak and the duration of the bloom (Fig. 6). The third type describes the composition of taxa in the phytoplankton community. Table 1 lists all the indicators as suggested by Platt & Sathyendranath (2008). Especially the indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton biomass are widely used to describe the timing and magnitude of phytoplankton blooms (Henson et al., 2006; Ho et al., 2017; Hopkins et al., 2015; Sapiano et al., 2012).

To calculate these indices, first the bloom events have to be detected. For this purpose, a chl-a concentration time series (for example, using OCRS data) has to be created. The data points can be averaged over time to fill missing values, creating a data set with weekly or lower temporal resolution. In some cases, a Gaussian model is fitted to the chlorophyll-a data (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Song et al., 2010). This data series can then be used to detect bloom events. Two methods are common to achieve this:

1. Threshold method: A fixed or variable threshold is defined. Every higher value is classified as a bloom. The most common threshold is the yearly median of chl-a plus an offset (e.g. 5% of the median) (Brody, Lozier, & Dunne, 2013; Groetsch et al., 2016; Racault et al., 2015; Soppa, Völker, & Bracher, 2016).
2. The rate of change is calculated for the data or the fitted model. The point of the most rapid increase is determined as the initiation of the bloom (Brody, Lozier, and Dunne, 2013; Groetsch et al., 2016).

Figure 6: Indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton biomass on a simplified bloom curve. Initiation signifies the start of the bloom, amplitude signifies the maximum of the time series, peak timing signifies the date of the maximum and duration signifies the time from start till end of the bloom. Taken from Platt & Sathyendranath (2008).

Table 1: Ecosystem indicators to measure dynamics in phytoplankton biomass, primary production and community structure (Platt and Sathyendranath, 2008)

Type	Indicator
Indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton biomass	Initiation of spring bloom
	Amplitude of spring bloom
	Timing of spring maximum
	Duration of spring bloom
Indicators for the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton production	Total production in spring bloom
	Annual phytoplankton production
	Generalized phytoplankton loss rate
	Integrated phytoplankton loss
	Annual-scale f-ratio
	Spatial variance in biomass field
	Spatial variance in production field
Indicators describing changes in community structure	Phytoplankton functional types
	Delineation of biogeochemical provinces
	Phytoplankton size structure

3 Study region

In this chapter the physical properties of the NoS and BaS are outlined. The seasonality, common species and past changes of species composition and phenology are presented. Figure 7 shows the location of both seas in the North of Europe and Fig. 8 the mean chl-a and SST seasonality for two exemplary regions of each sea.

3.1 North Sea

The North Sea is a coastal sea bounded by the British Isles, the Scandinavian peninsula, and the European mainland. It has a size of 575 300 km² and is relatively shallow with an average depth of 70 m. Yet, it is more than 100m deep in almost half of its area and therefore has an oceanic character in large parts. The physical state of the off-shore NoS is strongly influenced by the Atlantic Ocean, adjacent in the west, which brings in water of high salinity. In the east, there is a water exchange between NoS and BaS through Kattegat and Skagerrak. The salty NoS waters are

Figure 7: Location of NoS and BaS. Average chl-a concentration in European waters, 2007. Taken from NASA (2007).

distributed into the BaS through the upper layer while the brackish Baltic waters flow out near the bottom of the sea (BSH, n.d.; Müller, 2010; Peters et al., 2005). The currents in the shallow parts of the NoS are mainly controlled by the lunar tides but also by atmospheric winds (Müller, 2010; Scharfe, 2013).

Between April and May, rising temperatures trigger a stratification of the sea which is dissolved in November, followed by mixing of the water body in winter (Elliott and Clarke, 1991). In shallow coastal areas, the summer stratification is prohibited by the movements of the tides (BSH, n.d.).

Temperature induced stratification and mixing are also drivers of phytoplankton phenology. In winter, nutrient concentrations (mainly nitrogen, phosphorus, silicate and ammonia) increase in the

upper surface layers due to low productivity and wind induced mixing, which brings up nutrients from deeper sea layers. Increasing light in spring induces phytoplankton blooms. Warming temperatures onset water stratification which helps plankton populations to stay in the euphotic zone. In summer, the majority of nutrients are consumed by the phytoplankton leading to an end of the bloom. Mixing events due to strong winds in autumn redistribute nutrients into the upper layer and trigger a second bloom phase (see Fig.8) (BSH, 2017b; Johns and Reid, 2001).

The most important phytoplankton groups are diatoms (Bacillariophyta), which dominate during spring, dinoflagellates (Dinophyceae), which dominate during summer and micro algae of various taxonomic groups (BSH, 2017b; Reid et al., 1990).

Regarding the trend of chl-a in the NoS, inconclusive results are found in the literature. Though nutrient concentrations decreased in the NoS, McQuatters-Gollop et al. (2007) have found increased chl-a concentrations which they connect to clearer water and climate variability. However, Capuzzo et al. (2018) found declining primary production which are strongly connected to decreasing chl-a. In the NoS, the spring bloom has mostly been studied in areas near the shore while little literature exists on off-shore areas.

3.2 Baltic Sea

The BaS is a semi-enclosed inland sea with an area of 412 560 km² (Zhang et al., 2017). As can be seen in Fig. 7, it is enclosed by Scandinavia and the European mainland and ends at the Skagerrak where its water body is connected to the NoS (Peters et al., 2005). With an average depth of 52 m and salinities between 0 and 18 psu it is both relatively shallow and brackish (HELCOM, 2018; IOW, 2014). The mean SST lies between 8 and 10 °C, it is therefore colder than the NoS. There are distinct horizontal gradients in salinity and SST which both decrease from South to North. Additionally, there is a vertical gradient in salinity, the halocline, with lowest values in the surface layer (HELCOM, 2018; Zhang et al., 2017). In the summer months, there is also strong thermal stratification (BSH, 2017a).

According to Schernewski, Hofstede, & Neumann (2011), there is both an increase in temperature and a decrease in salinity which is associated to climate change. Kahru et al. (2016) have found that the number of days of the year with SST over 17 °C has almost doubled (from 29 days in 1982 to 56 days in 2014).

But this is not the only stressor on the ecosystems of the BaS, which is also impacted by a strong eutrophication. This goes back to anthropogenic activities in the 1970s when increased loads of nitrogen and phosphate from agriculture and industry have been deposited into the sea. These processes resulted in an increase in chl-a concentrations between the 70s and 90s (BSH, 2017a). According to IOW (2012), the trend has now stagnated even though the concentrations are still high compared to the pre-1970 situation. But Kahru et al. (2016) have detected an increasing trend for the 1998–2013 time series of mean chlorophyll in central BaS. They found that the number of days with concentrations above 3 mg/m³ has doubled from 110 to 220 days per year. Figure 7 shows the mean chl-a concentration in 2007 which ranges from 3 to 30 mg/m³ and is distinctly higher in the BaS than in the NoS.

More than 800 phytoplankton species live in the BaS (IOW, 2012). Important groups include diatoms (Bacillariophyta), dinoflagellates (Dinophyceae), micro algae of various taxonomic groups and cyanobacteria (Cyanobacteria) (BSH, 2017a).

The typical phytoplankton phenology in the BaS is constituted of two bloom events one occurring in summer and one in spring (see Fig.8). The spring bloom, which is dominated by diatoms (BSH, 2017a), starts first in the southern BaS during early March and then follows a temporal North-South gradient. The latest spring blooms occur during May in the Gulf of Finland (Zhang et al., 2017).

Both spring and summer blooms start increasingly earlier – a change that is connected to anthropogenic climate change (Kahru, Elmgren, and Savchuk, 2016). Another change in bloom phenology is the shift of chlorophyll concentration maxima. While spring blooms used to display the annual chl-a maximum, after the 1980s these maxima were now found during the summer bloom in July (Kahru, Elmgren, and Savchuk, 2016).

This is connected to the increase in cyanobacteria blooms which predominately occur in the later half of the year. Cyanobacteria benefit from increasing temperatures, high nutrient concentrations and low salinity, thus, finding increasingly convenient conditions in the BaS (BSH, 2017a; Jaanus et al., 2011; Kahru et al., 2016).

These cyanobacteria blooms lead to extremely high chl-a concentrations and sometimes form a dense floating layer on the sea surface, also known as floating scum. This makes it very difficult to correctly estimate chl-a concentrations using remote sensing data, especially in the summer months (Hieronymi et al., 2015). Another challenge in regard to remote sensing, is the high concentration of CDOM in the BaS which is highly absorbing and difficult to separate from phytoplankton pigments (Hieronymi et al., 2015; Kahru, Elmgren, and Savchuk, 2016)

Figure 8: Mean SST (red) and chl-a seasonality of two NoS regions (top) and two BaS regions (bottom). The BaS regions display a second summer bloom that is stronger than the spring bloom, while the second bloom of the NoS is in autumn and weaker than the spring bloom.

4 Methods

In the following chapter, the data used in this study is presented. The steps of preprocessing are described. The methods for relationship analysis of parameters, MHW detection, bloom event detection and relationship analysis of events are also described. Figure 9 shows the workflow and gives an overview of the input data, output data and the work steps.

4.1 Data

This thesis is mainly based on daily raster-data derived from satellite remote sensing. The variables and their properties are listed in Tab. 2.

Table 2: Overview of the data used in this thesis.

Variable	Source	Data-type	Spatial resolution	Unit	Temporal information
Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a)	OC-CCI	Raster	4km/pixel	mg/m ³	Daily, 1998-2018
Sea Surface Temperature (SST)	BSH	Raster	1km/pixel	°C	Daily, 1990-2018
Wind u-vector	ECMWF	Raster	80km/pixel	m/s	Daily, 1990-2018
Wind v-vector	ECMWF	Raster	80km/pixel	m/s	Daily, 1990-2018
Total cloud cover (TCC)	ECMWF	Raster	80km/pixel	%	Daily, 1990-2018
Marine Sea Regions	DWD	Shape	-	-	-

4.1.1 Chlorophyll-a

The Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative (OC-CCI) provides quality controlled climate variables based on OCS data. For this work, daily chl-a raster in mg/m³ (version 4.0) ranging from 1998 until 2018 with a resolution of 4km/pixel were used. It is provided by the ESA (2019).

Figure 9: The workflow of this thesis. Orange: Input data, yellow: preprocessing methods, green: preprocessed data (daily means), red: main methods, blue: output data.

To calculate chl-a concentrations, the OC-CCI blended different ocean colour algorithms (OCI, OC3 and OC5) and used them on composites of remote sensing reflectance. These composites are based on the data of the sensors MODIS - Aqua, VIIRS and SeaWiFS. While earlier versions of the OC-CCI chl-a data focused on applications in open ocean case-1 waters, version 4.0 aims to offer improved performance for case-2 waters as well (Jackson et al., 2019).

4.1.2 Sea surface temperature

Sea surface temperature (SST) represents the temperature (T) in the skin surface layer of a water body and therefore is the best available estimate for temperature in the euphotic zone. SST can be remotely sensed by measuring the seas radiation in the infra-red part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Due to the restricted penetration of infra-red radiation through the water column only the SST of the top few tens of micrometers of the sea surface can be measured. This skin is often a few tenths of degree cooler than the temperature a few centimeters below (ESA, n.d.).

Daily SST raster in °C over a 29 year period and with a spatial resolution of 1km/pixel were provided by the Bundesamt für Schifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH). They were created using Metop-01, NOAA-19 (AVHRR) as well as Sentinel-3 A and B data (BSH, n.d.; Schumacher, 2019).

4.1.3 Total cloud cover and wind speed

Total cloud cover (TCC) gives the percentage of the sky or, in the case of raster analysis, the percentage of a pixel, which is hidden by visible clouds. TCC affects the light available for phytoplankton photosynthesis. Wind speed describes the speed of moving air masses. It is connected to the mixing of the water body and therefore has an impact on phytoplankton growth. ERA (European Reanalysis) Interim data, which is a global atmospheric reanalysis product from the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) offer raster time series of these variables. This data was provided by Dee et al. (2011)

. Daily raster of TCC, the u- vector and the v-vector for the 10 meter wind component were downloaded. The spatial resolution is 80 km/pixel. Wind vectors and TCC are based on satellite retrievals from radiance data from different satellites.

4.1.4 Marine sea regions

A shape of 20 marine sea regions was provided by Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD, 2018). The NoS is constituted of 11 regions, the BaS of 9. The map in Fig. 10 provides all regions and their names. These regions are used by the DWD for shipping weather forecasts. Since a full evaluation of all twenty regions was beyond the scope of this work, ten focus regions (five in each sea) of similar size were picked. These regions represent a North-South gradient. These regions are evaluated in more detail. Region 7, the Ijsselmeer, is distinctly smaller than all other regions and has, due to the strong coastal influence and its secluded position, a deviant ecologic character. Therefore, it was excluded from most of the analysis.

Figure 10: Map of the twenty sea regions, including the ten focus regions, used to calculate daily means.

North Sea: 1. Engl. Channel West, 2. Engl. Channel East, 3. Southwestern North Sea, 4. Dogger, 5. Forties, 6. Viking, 7. Ijsselmeer, 8. German Bight, 9. Fisher, 10. Utsire, 11. Skagerrak

Baltic Sea: 12. Kattegat, 13. Great Belt, 14. Western Baltic Sea, 15. Rügen East, 16. Southern Baltic Sea, 17. Southeastern Baltic Sea, 18. Central Baltic Sea, 19. Northern Baltic Sea, 20. Gulf of Riga

4.2 Preprocessing

The polygons of the twenty marine sea regions were used to clip the daily raster of SST, Chl-a, TCC and u- and v-wind vectors. Daily means and standard deviations were calculated for each region. For chl-a, the percentage of valid, cloud-free pixels was calculated as well. Chl-a has a high standard deviation and can vary both strongly temporarily as well as spatially. Therefore, days that had less than 20% of valid pixels were dismissed and their means replaced with NA (not available). Daily u- and v-wind vector means were used to calculate the daily mean wind speed (v) for each region:

$$v = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$$

For SST and chl-a, the daily climatology was calculated using a sliding window method as described by Hobday et al. (2016). For each day of the year, a window of 11 days centering around the respective day was used to calculate the mean of the 11 days and ascribe it to the center day. This climatology is showing the average annual behavior of each parameter. Since cloud cover is too high in winter, the time period for 1st of November until 31st of January was excluded from the data.

4.3 Correlations between chl-a and meteorological parameters

To analyze the relationship of each of the three meteorological parameters (SST, TCC, wind speed) with chl-a, monthly means of all parameters over all years were calculated. For each of the three meteorological parameters and chl-a, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated in each region. The significance level $p = 0.05$ was chosen.

4.4 MHW detection

Marine heatwaves were detected using the method proposed by Hobday et al. (2016). According to them, MHW are identified relative to a threshold which is based on the regional climatological mean temperature. The corresponding R-package "heatwaveR" created by Schlegel & Smit (2019) and its function "detect_event", which applies this framework, was used on the data. The core principles of the MHW detection are shown in Fig. 12.

The 29 years of SST observations were used as the climatology baseline period. In a first step, the threshold value was calculated. The threshold for each day of the year (DOY) is defined as the 90th percentile of the temperature distribution of all data points over the whole baseline period in the 11-day window centering around a day of interest. This means that the temperature distribution for each DOY is made up of 319 data points (11 * 29). An example is shown in Fig 11.

Figure 11: Density function of SST for the 1st of May (DOY 122) in the Gulf of Riga. The black graph shows the distribution of all measured SST in the 11 day window (DOY 117 -127) centering around the 1st of May. The red line signifies the 90th percentile of the distribution which is used as the threshold for MHW events.

A time period was classified as an MHW when the temperature was above the threshold for at least five days. If two events were separated by two days or less, they were merged into one event, even when one of the events was shorter than five days.

The "heatwaveR" package provides algorithms for the calculation of an abundance of MHW event indices. The ones used in this work are presented in Tab. 3. Most important for this work are: duration, mean intensity (I_{mean}) and maximum intensity (I_{max}). The intensity is defined as the difference between the daily temperature and the climatology. Additionally, the yearly frequency (MHW days per year) for each region was calculated. MHW were categorized into the four categories: moderate, strong, severe and extreme as proposed by Hobday et al. (2018) The threshold of each category is defined as the multiple of the difference between the 90th percentile and the climatological mean, as can be seen in Fig. 13. On a day with the climatological mean of 10 °C and the 90th percentile-threshold of 12 °C, the difference of those two would be 2 °C. Therefore, the threshold for a moderate MHW would be 12 °C, for a strong MHW 14 °C (12 + 2 °C) for a severe MHW 16 °C (12 + (2*2)°C) and for an extreme MHW 18 °C (12 + (3*2) °C). One day of temperatures above the threshold of the next higher category is enough to assign the MHW to that category.

Table 3: Overview of the MHW event indices used in this work.

Name	Description	Unit
Mean intensity (I_{mean})	Mean difference between T and climatology during the MHW	°C
Max intensity (I_{max})	Maximum difference between T and climatology during the MHW	°C
Duration	Length of the MHW	days
Frequency	Number of MHW days per year	days/year
Category	4 categories: moderate, strong, severe and extreme. Defined by the maximum intensity of the MHW	-

Figure 12: Schematic graphic of an MHW. When the temperature (black line) crosses the threshold at the 90th percentile climatology (green line) for at least five days, the event is considered an MHW. An MHW can be described by using event indices like intensity (I), start, end, peak date or duration. Taken from Hobday et al. (2016).

The Mann-Kendall trend test was previously used successfully by Soppa et al. (2016) to test developments in event indices. Using the R-package “Kendall” (McLeod, 2011), the test was performed to analyze temporal trends for yearly mean I_{max} , yearly mean MHW duration and MHW frequency for each region. Kendall’s rank correlation measures the strength of the monotonic relationship between the vectors x and y . Kendall’s rank correlation coefficient, τ , maybe expressed as $\tau=S/D$ where

$$S = \sum_{i < j} (\text{sign}(x_j - x_i)) * (\text{sign}(y_j - y_i))$$

and

$$D = n(n-1)/2 .$$

n stands for the number of observations. The *sign* signifies if a number is positive, negative or zero.

Therefore, it can be defined as follows:

$$\text{sign}(x) \begin{cases} 1 \text{ if } x > 0 \\ 0 \text{ if } x = 0 \\ -1 \text{ if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$\tau = -1$ indicates a monotonic declining trend and $\tau = 1$ indicates a monotonic increasing trend (McLeod, 2015).

Figure 13: Schematic graphic of the MHW categorization framework. Multiples of the difference between the threshold (90th percentile) and mean climatology (bold black line) represent the thresholds for the four categories (moderate, strong, severe, extreme). If the temperature (dashed line) during an MHW crosses a threshold for at least one day it is categorized as the respective category, in this instance „extreme“. Taken from Hobday et al. (2018).

4.5 Bloom detection

To detect phytoplankton blooms, a threshold approach (as used by Thomalla et al. (2011) and Sapiano et al. (2012)) was applied. An event is categorized as a bloom when the chl-a values rise above a certain threshold for a certain amount of time. Missing values in the daily chlorophyll data from 1st of February until 31st of October were interpolated with linear interpolation using the function “na.approx” from the R-package “zoo” (Zeileis et al., 2019)

If the first value of the time series was missing, it was filled with the annual mean.

Plankton growth and decline is extremely variable and interpolations of longer time periods can produce great uncertainties.. Therefore, a sliding window method was used to flag periods with too little valid measurements (Fig. 14). A window of nine days centering around the data point in question was set. If more than 6 data points in the window were missing from the original data (prior to interpolation), the center point of the window was flagged as invalid. Invalid time periods were excluded from the following processes. This way periods with little valid measurements (e.g. periods with high cloud coverage) are excluded from the analysis.

The threshold (s) was defined as

$$s = \text{median} + 0.1 * \text{median} .$$

The start and end of a bloom were defined as the day the data (chl-a) would increase over the threshold (start) and the day before it would fall below the threshold (end).

Figure 14: Schematic of the moving window method used to remove „unreliable“ time periods. If in a window of five days (black bracket) more than six data points are missing (boxes with NA) the target date in the window’s center (red box) will be flagged (dashed lines) and excluded from interpolation and further analysis.

The condition for chl- a_i to be classified as bloom start was therefore:

$$chl-a_i < s \ \& \ chl-a_{i+1} > s$$

While the condition for chl- a_i to be classified as the bloom end was :

$$chl-a_i > s \ \& \ chl-a_{i+1} < s$$

Chl- a tends to pulsate previous to a bloom event, often exceeding the threshold s for a short amount of time (Racault et al., 2015). To prevent the over estimation of blooms, events which were shorter than 7 days were excluded from the following process and blooms which were less than 6 days apart were merged into one event (Fig. 15).

Figure 15: Schematic of the bloom detection. If a the chl- a concentration rises above the threshold (orange line, $s = \text{median} + 0.1 * \text{median}$) for at least seven days, the event is classified as a bloom (green line). Should two events occur less than six days apart, they are merged into one event. In this case the first event is too short (two days). The second event reaches the critical number of seven days and is merged with the third event, which happens only two days later.

Bloom events can be described with temporal event indices (start, end, peak date) and event indices of magnitude (peak value, length, sum) (Racault et al., 2012). The indices are displayed in Tab. 4 and Fig. 16.

Because of the great insecurities connected to chl- a measurements in the BaS during summer, it was decided to analyze only spring bloom events. Therefore, the detected bloom events had to be classified into “spring” and “others”. This was done using the chl- a seasonality as a reference. The threshold approach was also used on the chl- a seasonality to detect the average bloom seasonality. Sometimes a third very short events could be present in February. Therefore, it was not possible to simply classify the first bloom as the spring bloom. Assuming that each region has one to two major

bloom phases (spring bloom and in some cases a second summer or autumn bloom), the two longest bloom events in the chl-a seasonality were identified. The first one of this set was classified as the reference spring bloom phase.

Table 4: Overview of the bloom event indices used in this work

Type	Name	Description	Unit
Temporal	Start	First day the chl-a concentration is above the threshold	DOY
	End	Last day the chl-a concentration is above the threshold	DOY
	Peak date	Date of the maximum chl-a concentration between start and end	DOY
Magnitude	Peak value	Maximum chl-a concentration between start and end	mg/m ³
	Length	Duration of the event (start to end)	days
	Sum	Sum of daily chl-a concentrations from start to end	mg/m ³

Figure 16: Schematic graph of an exemplary bloom event and its event indices. The relationship between MHW and a bloom was examined for MHW occurring in the 30 days before a bloom (pre-bloom phase) and during the bloom event (bloom phase).

This reference phase was used to classify the detected bloom events. An event was considered a spring bloom if its peak date was found in a time window twice the length of the reference spring bloom centering around the peak of the reference bloom (Fig. 17).

Figure 17: Schematic of the method to classify spring blooms. The first of the two longest bloom events of the chl-a seasonality (green line) was classified as the spring bloom. Any event in the chl-a timeseries which peaked during the spring bloom window is classified as a spring bloom event. This window is a time period twice the size of the reference bloom and centering around the reference blooms peak.

Finally, the Mann-Kendall trend test was used to analyze trends in bloom indices (see previous chapter for the formula). For trend testing of the start, the start dates of the first bloom event of every year were applied, for the end, the end of the last bloom event. For length, sum and peak value the maxima of the respective indices of all events in one year was used. This was done because the spring bloom phase can consist of between one to five bloom events. Using means for the Mann-Kendall test would contort the results.

4.6 Relationship of MHW and blooms

Spearman's rank correlation coefficient between MHW indices and bloom indices was calculated to analyze a relationship between MHW and spring bloom events (Fig. 18).

For this purpose all spring bloom events which occurred at the same time as an MHW event were identified. Also all spring bloom events which had an MHW during the thirty days before the bloom pre-bloom phase were identified (Fig. 16). The aim was to find out, if there was a different relationship between MHW and bloom if the MHW happened before or during the bloom.

For each phase (pre-bloom phase and bloom phase), I_{\max} and the number of MHW days during the phase were calculated.

These two MHW indices were used to calculate Spearman's correlation for bloom start, end, length, peak value and sum. In many sea regions, less than five bloom events that occurred at the same time as an MHW were found. Since the minimum sample size to calculate correlations is five, all events that fit the criteria in the NoS and respectively in the BaS were combined and correlations for both seas were calculated.

Figure 18: Flowchart for the calculation of correlation coefficients (blue) between two MHW event indices (red) and five bloom event indices (green). Separate correlations were calculated for MHW occurring in the pre-bloom phase and MHW occurring during the actual bloom (main bloom phase).

5 Results

Here, the results derived from the described methods are presented. The relationship of chl-a to respectively wind speed, TCC and SST is compared. The properties and developments of MHW and spring blooms are presented. Finally, the relationship of MHW and spring bloom is described in the last section.

5.1 Relationship between chl-a and TCC, wind speed and SST

Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to calculate correlations between chl-a and respectively TCC, wind speed and SST, which are shown in Fig. 19. Weak but predominately significant negative correlations between chl-a and TCC for both BaS and NoS with a range between -0.1 and -0.37 were found. Thus, the higher the TCC, the lower are the chl-a concentrations. The strongest correlations are found in July for both seas.

The correlation between wind and chl-a depends on the season. For both seas, there is a weak positive correlation from February till March. In spring, this relationship changes and significant negative correlations are displayed for the second half of the year, which are slightly stronger in the NoS. There is a weak tendency of lower chl-a concentrations during higher wind speed, especially after June.

While TCC and wind speed show homogeneous tendencies for both seas, correlations between SST and chl-a draw an entirely different pictures. SST displays correlation of higher variance and a more diverse pattern in a much larger range. Moreover, the correlations distinctly differ between BaS and NoS. In the NoS, more than half of the correlations are negative, indicating a negative impact of SST on chl-a concentrations, while in the BaS, the majority is positive, indicating a positive impact. October is an exception for the BaS, as it is the only month with entirely negative measures. Correlations in the NoS range between 0.27 and -0.5, in the BaS between 0.44 and -0.27.

Figure 19: Pearson's correlation coefficients between monthly mean chl-a concentrations and monthly TCC, wind speed and SST in the NoS (left) and BaS (right). Significant correlations are represented by a filled circle, insignificant ones are empty.

5.2 Spatial and temporal distribution of MHW

In the following chapter, the spatial and temporal distribution of MHW in the study region as well as trends in SST and MHW are presented. All detected MHW are listed in the Appendix I (Sec).

5.2.1 SST & MHW Indices

An overview of distribution of MHW indices in the study region is given in Figure 20 as well as in Tab. 5.

On average, SST in the NoS (1.7 °C) is higher than in the BaS (9.3 °C). As can be see in Fig. 20a, there is a distinct North-South gradient for mean SST in both seas. Warmest temperatures are found in the English Channel and coldest in the North of the BaS.

It was found that MHW occurred all over the study region with a high variability regarding their number and indices. Most MHW (totaling over the study period of 29 years) were found in the Gulf of Riga (61) while the smallest amount occurred in the Southwestern NoS (33). On average, more MHW occurred in BaS regions (46.7) than in the NoS (41.5) but the NoS regions are hit more often by strong and severe MHW (Fig. 20f and g). Strong MHW are experienced all over the study region (average for NoS regions: 13.6; average for BaS regions: 11.8) but only three BaS regions witnessed a single severe MHW while twice as much NoS regions witnessed one to two severe MHW. The only extreme MHW in the study region occurred in 2009 in Viking (NoS). When it comes to the frequency (number of days per year) for each of the four categories, BaS has a higher frequency for moderate and strong MHW, but NoS has a higher frequency for severe and extreme MHW (Tab. 5).

But even though MHW of higher categories occur more often in the NoS, the MHW in the BaS are on average longer and more intense (Fig 20b and c). There is an apparent West-East gradient for both intensity measures (I_{mean} and I_{max}) with lowest intensities in the western NoS and highest in the BaS. The most intense MHW occur in the Gulf of Riga. The average duration of MHW does display a more random pattern (Fig. 20b). The Southern BaS has the longest MHW while English Channel East, Dogger, Forties and Gulf of Riga have the shortest.

Gulf of Riga had both the MHW with the highest I_{mean} (5.8 °C in 1997) and the highest I_{max} (8.1 °C in 2016). The longest MHW took place in the Southern BaS in 2007 (95 days). 2014 was the year with most MHW (92) and MHW days (1067) for the NoS. In the BaS, the most MHW occurred in 2014 (38) while the most MHW days occurred in 2006 (507 days).

Table 5: Average values for SST and different MHW indices in NoS and BaS.

	SST	SST trend	Frequency of moderate MHW	Frequency strong MHW	Frequency severe MHW	Frequency extreme MHW
North Sea	10.7 °C	0.36	81.4	65.2	5	0.4
Baltic Sea	9.3 °C	0.44	111.8	76.1	1.2	0

Figure 20: Maps of MHW indices in the study region. a) Yearly mean SST. b) Mean MHW duration in days. c) Mean I_{mean} . d) Mean I_{max} . e) Total number of MHW events. f) Number of strong MHW events. g) Number of severe MHW events. h) Number of extreme MHW events.

5.2.2 Trend analysis

Mann-Kendall trend test was applied to SST and MHW indices. The results are presented in Tab. 6. The strongest trend is found for SST, which is rising in the whole study region (Fig 21). The Mann-Kendall test resulted overall in positive significant trends. Temperatures increase slightly faster in the BaS than in the NoS (Tab. 6).

There is a North-South gradient for the slope of the trend in the BaS with a slower increase in the South and a faster increase in the North. The increase is more uniform in the NoS.

Both NoS and BaS show an increasing trend in number of MHW and number of MHW days for all four categories. While the Mann-Kendall test showed that the rising trend for the number of MHW days is significant for only five regions (three in NoS and two in BaS), it has to be noted that the trend is positive for all regions. This can also be seen in Fig. 22 and 23.

The trend for maximum intensity is predominantly negative but weak and insignificant with the exception of English Channel West (significant positive trend of 0.48) and Dogger (significant negative trend of -0.39). The trends in MHW duration are incoherent, with both weak positive and negative values for the study region (Fig. 22 and 23). The exceptions are the two regions in the English Channel which both display a significant positive trend.

Figure 21: Yearly mean SST in the ten focus regions in NoS (left) and BaS (right). An increasing trend is apparent for all regions.

Table 6: Kendall's rank correlation coefficient, τ , calculated by using the Mann-Kendall trend test for yearly mean MHW even indices (frequency, I_{\max} , duration) and yearly mean SST. Significant trends are in bold ($p < 0.05$).

No.	Name	MHW Frequency	MHW I_{\max}	MHW Duration	Mean SST
North Sea					
1	Engl. Channel West	0.29	0.48	0.56	0.29
2	Engl. Channel East	0.23	0.00	0.59	0.33
3	Southwestern North Sea	0.18	0.35	0.20	0.31
4	Dogger	0.27	-0.39	-0.21	0.38
5	Forties	0.09	-0.03	-0.13	0.38
6	Viking"	0.38	0.01	0.21	0.37
7	Ijsselmeer	0.27	-0.22	0.16	0.42
8	German Bight	0.13	-0.06	-0.09	0.35
9	Fisher	0.12	-0.22	-0.10	0.37
10	Utsire	0.16	-0.11	0.02	0.40
11	Skagerrak	0.13	-0.21	-0.10	0.37
Baltic Sea					
12	Kattegat	0.23	-0.12	-0.05	0.38
13	Great Belt	0.20	-0.10	0.10	0.38
14	Western Baltic Sea	0.24	-0.23	0.00	0.38
15	Rügen East	0.19	-0.26	-0.17	0.46
16	Southern Baltic Sea	0.18	-0.05	0.02	0.34
17	Southeastern Baltic Sea	0.22	-0.15	0.18	0.48
18	Central Baltic Sea	0.25	-0.19	0.08	0.47
19	Northern Baltic Sea	0.30	-0.23	0.19	0.55
20	Gulf of Riga	0.32	-0.18	0.08	0.53

Figure 22: Yealy number of total MHW events, number of MHW days (frequency), number of strong MHW events, mean MHW duration and I_{\max} for the five focus regions of the NoS.

Figure 23: Yealy number of total MHW events, number of MHW days (frequency), number of strong MHW events, mean MHW duration and I_{\max} for the five focus regions of the BaS.

5.2.3 Seasonality of MHW

An apparent seasonality of MHW was not found. Fig. 24 shows the mean temporal distribution of MHW for both seas. The temporal distribution in the focus regions can be seen in Fig. 30 and 31. MHW days are irregularly distributed, showing that MHW can occur anytime during the year. In the BaS, July and September are relatively strong months for MHW while April is the weakest month. In the NoS, June and July are the month with most and February the month with the least MHW but the differences are far less distinct. Summer and autumn tend to be a stronger MHW seasons than winter and spring but even that is not the case in all regions. For example, the Southern BaS experiences most of its MHW in December. Many regions present a low point in the spring months. Especially in the BaS, April is very weak compared to the rest of the year.

The monthly mean I_{\max} is presented in Fig. 25. There are apparent differences between the sea regions. While I_{\max} is almost equally distributed over all months in the southern regions of NoS (English Channel and Southwestern NoS), there is an increase after April and a distinct peak during either June or July in the northern regions. In the BaS, I_{\max} is highest between May, June, July and/or August. It is lowest in April or May.

Figure 24: Sum of MHW days between 1990 and 2018 per months in the NoS (left) and BaS (right).

Figure 25: Mean I_{max} per month in six NoS regions (top) and six BaS regions (bottom) from 1990 until 2018.

5.3 Properties of the spring bloom

Nineteen out of twenty marine sea regions were analyzed regarding their mean chl-a concentrations and their spring bloom events. All detected spring bloom events for these regions are presented in Appendix II (Sec).

5.3.1 Spatial and temporal distribution of mean chl-a during spring

Figure 26: Maps of spring bloom indices in the study region. a) Mean chl-a in mg/m³ from 1st of February until 30th of May. b) Mean bloom sum of the spring bloom events. c) Mean DOY of the start of spring bloom events. d) Mean length of spring bloom events in days.

The regions show a high variability of mean chl-a during spring bloom time (1st of February until 30th of May) with a range between 0.9 (Viking) and 14.2 mg/m³ (Gulf of Riga) (Fig. 26a) . The absolute range for daily means in the study region lies between 0.3 and 40 mg/m³. Mean

concentrations are distinctly higher in the BaS than the NoS (Fig. 26a). There is an apparent West-East gradient. Concentrations are lowest in the regions closest to the Atlantic Ocean and highest in the Gulf of Riga. Regions close to the Atlantic like Dogger, Forties and Viking show not only very low mean concentrations but also very weak concentration peaks in their chl-a seasonality (Fig. 27). Regions which are close to the main-land coast like Southwestern NoS and German Bight have higher mean concentrations and a more prominent spring bloom peak.

Chl-a means in the BaS show a more homogeneous picture than the NoS. The majority of regions (six out of nine) have a spring mean concentration between 4 and 8 mg/m³. Gulf of Riga is a prominent exception. While most regions have a chl-a seasonality peak between 4 and 8 mg/m³, the mean peak of Gulf of Riga reaches a value of 20mg/m³ (Fig. 27). Absolute peak values can be twice as high or higher. The majority of spring bloom peaks lies between the 100th and 150th DOY.

Figure 27: Mean chl-a seasonality in mg/m³ in the ten focus regions in the NoS (left) and BaS (right). A chl-a peak can be seen for all regions.

5.3.2 Spring bloom indices

There is a high variability in spring bloom events, both regarding the indices of timing as well as of magnitude. Figure 28 displays the variability for start, end, length, peak value and number of spring blooms for then ten focus regions. On average blooms start on the 75th DOY. Earliest bloom starts happen in Dogger (on average 47th DOY), latest starts in Gulf of Riga (on average 101st DOY) (Fig. 26c). In both seas, a North-South gradient is evident regarding the mean start time of the spring bloom, which is starts earlier in the south and later in the north. In the NoS, the spring bloom also starts early in the regions strongly influenced by BaS waters. One exception is the English Channel

where, even though it is the furthest South, the spring bloom starts on average in March and not in February like in the neighboring regions to the west. In general, bloom events start earlier in the NoS (70th DOY) than the BaS (86th DOY). The end of the bloom season is defined by the last day of the last spring bloom event. The margin of the end day is much smaller than for the start day (130th DOY in Dogger and 173rd DOY in Gulf of Riga) and the average end day is much less variable: the vast majority of regions have a mean end of bloom events between the 140th and 160th DOY. The mean ends for both seas are extremely close as well (153rd DOY for the NoS and 152nd DOY for the BaS).

The mean peak date is strongly correlated with the mean start ($R = 0.89$) with both seas displaying similar spatial patterns to the start day (Fig 26c). As can be seen in Fig. 28, peaks can manifest during any time of the bloom event: right at the beginning, in the middle or towards the end.

The average length of bloom events vary strongly among regions (Fig. 26d). Shortest mean length is found in Rügen East (15.5 days), longest in Dogger (36 days). The range of absolute lengths is even bigger, reaching from 6 (the defined minimum) to 103 days. Bloom events in the NoS tend to be longer (27.2 days) than in the BaS (22.6 days).

The chl-a bloom sum is strongly correlated with mean chl-a concentration ($R = 0.95$), thus, a very similar spatial pattern can be seen (Fig. 26b). The bloom sum is weak in the majority of the NoS regions (0 to 100 mg/m³) with the exception of English Channel East and SW NoS (100-200mg/m³) and highest in BaS regions, especially in the Gulf of Riga (500-600 mg/m³). The majority of BaS regions have mean bloom sums between 200 and 300 mg/m³. The smallest absolute bloom sum measured was 4.1 mg/m³ (Forties), the highest was 1735 mg/m³ (Gulf of Riga).

The mean peak value is very homogeneous in the NoS, it lies between 0-10 mg/m³ in all regions.

In the BaS, the majority lies between 10-20 mg/m³, only 17 and 18 display 5-10 mg/m³ while Gulf of Riga is highest with 20 to 25 mg/m³.

The bloom length and bloom sum of spring blooms are significantly linearly correlated in all regions (min $R = 0.85$ and max $R = 0.97$). Peak value and sum are also significantly but weaker correlated (min $R = 0.55$ and max $R = 0.85$).

The Mann-Kendall test was used to analyze trends in indices. Table 7 displays the results for all regions. Seventeen out of nineteen regions show a trend towards an earlier start of the spring bloom (meaning a negative trend). This trend is only significant in two NoS regions (English Channel North and West) but significant for the five biggest BaS regions. Mann-Kendall test results on end, length and peak value are inconclusive, showing both negative and positive trends of which only

very few are significant. There are also mixed and inconclusive results for the bloom sum in the NoS. But the trend in peak value and bloom sum in the BaS is predominantly positive with four regions displaying a significant peak value trend.

Table 7: Kendall's rank correlation coefficient, τ , calculated by using the Mann-Kendall trend test for the spring bloom. For start, the start of the first spring bloom event per year was used, for end, the end of the last event. The maximum of length, peak value and sum of the spring bloom events per year was used. Significant trends are in bold ($p < 0.05$).

	Name	Start	End	Length	Peak Value	Sum
North Sea						
1	Engl. Channel West	-0.51	0.03	-0.30	-0.19	-0.34
2	Engl. Channel East	-0.46	-0.28	-0.04	0.01	0.01
3	Southwestern North Sea	-0.15	-0.07	0.17	-0.05	0.13
4	Dogger	0.05	-0.38	-0.11	0.23	0.00
5	Forties	0.03	-0.04	0.12	-0.02	0.09
7	Ijsselmeer	---	---	---	---	---
6	Viking"	-0.18	-0.13	0.00	-0.16	-0.13
8	German Bight	-0.14	-0.17	-0.01	-0.14	-0.04
9	Fisher	-0.04	0.20	0.00	-0.01	0.15
10	Utsire	-0.29	-0.14	0.42	0.23	0.55
11	Skagerrak	-0.08	0.03	0.32	0.27	0.37
Baltic Sea						
12	Kattegat	-0.06	-0.07	0.30	0.40	0.38
13	Great Belt	-0.02	-0.26	-0.13	0.21	0.08
14	Western Baltic Sea	-0.27	-0.33	0.17	0.61	0.32
15	Rügen East	-0.27	-0.17	-0.31	0.12	-0.05
16	Southern Baltic Sea	-0.37	-0.06	-0.03	0.15	0.20
17	Southeastern Baltic Sea	-0.43	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.09
18	Central Baltic Sea	-0.52	0.04	-0.13	0.43	0.24
19	Northern Baltic Sea	-0.47	-0.23	-0.24	0.59	0.27
20	Gulf of Riga	-0.38	0.05	0.11	0.26	0.19

5.4 Relationship between MHW and phytoplankton blooms

5.4.1 Correlations between event indices

Spearman's rank correlation coefficients were calculated for MHW indices (number of MHW days and I_{\max} during the bloom event) and bloom indices (start, end, length, peak value, sum) for MHW occurring during a) the pre-bloom phase of 30 days and b) the actual bloom phase. The pattern of MHW and spring blooms for the ten focus regions is displayed in Fig. 28. Table 8 lists the correlations for all indices.

Table 8: Spearman's correlations between MHW indices (I_{\max} , number of days) and bloom indices (start, end, length, peak value and sum) both for MHW occurring during the 30 days before a bloom event (pre-bloom phase, top of the table) and during a bloom event (bloom phase, bottom of the table), NoS is left of the table, BaS right of the table. Significant trends are in bold ($p < 0.05$).

	North Sea		Baltic Sea	
	MHW I_{\max}	No. of MHW days	MHW I_{\max}	No. of MHW days
a) Pre-bloom phase				
Bloom start	0.40	0.09	0.14	0.24
Bloom end	0.33	0.13	0.29	-0.05
Bloom length	-0.28	0.09	-0.02	-0.39
Bloom peak value	-0.05	0.26	-0.03	-0.34
Bloom sum	-0.18	0.20	0.07	-0.37
b) Bloom phase				
Bloom start	0.27	-0.27	0.55	-0.26
Bloom end	0.58	0.07	0.73	0.10
Bloom length	0.43	0.49	0.34	0.40
Bloom peak value	0.52	0.51	0.17	0.16
Bloom sum	0.54	0.61	0.35	0.34

Pre-bloom phase

For the pre-bloom phase, a positive relationship between both MHW indices and bloom start and bloom end was found (except for MHW days and bloom end in the BaS, where a weak and

insignificant negative correlation was found). There is a tendency towards a later bloom start and a later bloom end when an MHW occurs in the 30 days before the bloom. These findings were significant in the NoS and insignificant in the BaS.

Negative, significant correlations for bloom length, peak value and sum in the BaS were found. This indicates an overall negative relationship between MHW incidence before a bloom and the magnitude of the bloom in the BaS.

For the NoS, the results were not as conclusive. A negative, significant relationship between I_{\max} and bloom length but a positive, significant relationship between MHW days and bloom peak value were found.

Bloom phase

For the NoS there were significant positive relationships for I_{\max} and all bloom indices. This indicates later bloom starts and ends as well as longer and stronger blooms for bloom events that co-occur with an MHW. For MHW days and the bloom indices of magnitude, positive significant correlations were found as well. Opposing to the finding for I_{\max} , a significant negative relationship for MHW days and the bloom start was found.

There was a similar pattern for the BaS with the difference that the negative relationship between MHW days and bloom start is not significant while the positive one between I_{\max} and start is. All correlations for I_{\max} and the bloom indices are positive and, with the exception of peak value, all are significant. In regard to MHW days, significant positive relationships for length and sum were found. This indicates that in both NoS and BaS, MHW of greater intensity correlate with a later start and later end, a longer duration, higher peaks and a higher bloom sum. In contrast to that, longer MHW seem to correlate with an earlier start, but also correlate with longer and stronger blooms. In general, longer and more intense MHW correlate with blooms of higher magnitude. This relationship is also presented in Fig. 29, where the scatter plots for the relationship of the bloom indices of magnitude and I_{\max} are shown.

Figure 28: Spring bloom events (black lines) and MHW events (red lines) per year between 1998 and 2018. The y-axis shows the DOY. Bloom peak values in mg/m³ are represented by green dots. The NoS focus regions are on the right, BaS focus regions on the left.

Figure 29: Correlation of I_{\max} (y-axis) and bloom indices of magnitude: length, sum, peak value (x-axis) in the NoS (left) and BaS (right); r = Spearman's correlation coefficient.

5.4.2 Relationship of MHW and chl-a seasonalities

As described in Sec. 5.2.3, there is a no apparent seasonality in the distribution of MHW over the year. Many regions display a low point in MHW days during one or more spring months (March, April, May), (Fig. 30 and 31). Especially in the BaS, the majority of sea regions have a clear minimum of MHW days in April. This minimum often correlates with the peak of the chl-a seasonality, as can be seen in Fig. 31, which presents the spring chl-a seasonality together with the MHW seasonality. Four out of six BaS regions (Southeastern BaS, Central BaS, Northern BaS and Gulf of Riga) have a MHW minimum during the chl-a spring maximum in April. The other two (Kattegat and Southern BaS) have a low MHW frequency during the main spring bloom months of these regions (Feb, March and April) but here the highest mean chl-a concentration does not correspond with the lowest MHW frequency.

This pattern is not as clear in the NoS. Southwestern NoS, Dogger and German Bight also show an increase in MHW days parallel to the increase in chl-a concentrations until April which is then followed by a sudden decrease in May. Other distinct low points in MHW can be found in two regions during March and April (Viking and Utsire). Yet, in the NoS, these low points are only in one case (Utsire) simultaneous with the chl-a concentration peaks.

The low number of MHW during spring resulted in a small sample size co-occurring MHW and spring bloom events.

Figure 30: MHW and chl-a seasonality for six NoS regions. The left y-axis represents the total sum of MHW days per months between 1990 and 2018 (red bars). The right y-axis represents the mean chl-a concentration (mg/m³) during the spring months for the years 1998 – 2018 (grey bars).

Figure 31: MHW and chl-a seasonality for six BaS regions. The left y-axis represents the total sum of MHW days per months between 1990 and 2018 (red bars). The right y-axis represents the mean chl-a concentration (mg/m³) during the spring months for the years 1998 – 2018 (grey bars).

6 Discussion

In this chapter, the research questions from Sec 1 are answered. The findings are discussed and compared with results from other literature. Limitations of methods and data are presented.

6.1 General limits of the data and the methods

In principle, the methods for bloom and MHW detection used in this thesis can be applied to raster data as well. But since the long calculation times for raster time series was beyond the scope of this thesis regional means were used. Nonetheless, phytoplankton has a high spatial and temporal variability and high chlorophyll concentrations often appear on small spatial scales. Small scale phenomena are lost in this method and local relationships between SST, TCC, wind speed or MHW and bloom events could not be examined.

Platt et al. (2010) pointed out that averaging chl-a concentrations over an area, that covers more than one ecological province could result in misleading findings. The study region was not partitioned into biogeochemical provinces as Platt & Sathyendranath (2008) recommend. Instead, the meteorological sea regions as provided by the DWD were used. Yet, a different partitioning of the study region which is based on biogeochemical properties and more in accordance with the spatial and temporal distributions of blooms and MHW might lead to different results. Furthermore, the same methods would yield more detailed and conclusive results if applied to the original raster data.

As pointed out in Sec 3.2, many issues arise when trying to derive chl-a concentrations in the BaS. The data provided by OC-CCI used in this thesis is no exception. Hieronymi et al. (2015) performed validation on the OC-CCI data through matchup analysis and found divergence between the satellite and the in situ data (Fig. 32). They assign this divergence to the high concentrations in CDOM and to high concentrations of cyanobacteria in summer.

Analyzing only the spring bloom, a time when cyanobacteria are not dominant, might have helped to avoid this issue to some extent. Additionally, the data was averaged over big areas which probably smoothed out local errors connected to patches of high CDOM or floating algal scum. But eventually, without validation data, the chl-a concentrations calculated in this work should not be taken as absolutes but only as indicators for trends and relationships. This is not only true for the BaS regions but for the NoS regions as well, since to the knowledge of the author, no validation with in situ data has ever been done here for the OC-CCI data.

Additionally, the satellite derived data in use is limited to the surface chl-a concentration. Yet, phytoplankton can be unevenly distributed vertically and maxima might be found at depths that cannot be measured via remote sensing (Morel & Berthon, 1989).

The data used may also be biased due to interpolation of missing data and data that was flagged due to too high cloud cover. Interpolation of chl-a data is prone to errors because of the strong short-time variability of chl-a concentrations. Racault et al. (2015) and Groetsch et al. (2016) have avoided these issues by using daily concentrations to calculate means for longer time periods (8 days and 21 days).

Platt et al. (2010) have pointed out that longer averaging times decrease the number of lacking pixels due to cloud coverage. On the other hand, events happening on a short time scale are lost.

Since the analysis of MHW in this work is based on daily SST data, it was decided to stick to a daily resolution for the chl-a data as well. Future research on the topic of spring blooms in BaS and NoS should try to average chl-a over longer time periods and compare the results. Another possible approach would be the use of DINEOF (Data Interpolating Empirical Orthogonal Functions) which has been successfully used for interpolation of daily SST and chl-a raster data in the past (e.g. Miles, He, & Li, 2009; Shropshire, Li, & He, 2016). Ping, Su, & Meng (2016) have pointed out that DINEOF algorithms may cost long computational time. Therefore, it was decided that an application of DINEOF is beyond the scope of this thesis but it would probably improve interpolation results if used in future works.

Figure 32: Validation through matchup analysis of OC-CCI chl-a data (y-axis) and in-situ data (x-axis) in the BaS. The red crosses signify matchups on the 13th of July 2005 Taken from Hieronymi et al. (2015).

6.2 Relationship of chl-a and SST compared to other meteorological parameters

In this thesis, chl-a concentrations were used as a proxy for phytoplankton. Correlations of chl-a and SST were compared to correlations of chl-a and TCC as well as correlations of chl-a and wind speed. The results show that the relationship between SST and chl-a is far more complex, variable and in some cases much stronger than the relationship with the other two parameters. Wind speed and TCC show similar temporal correlation patterns in BaS and NoS and over all display weak but significant correlations that do not exceed -0.37 or 0.26. Correlations with TCC are constantly negative as a high cloud cover limits light supply. The major issue with this method is that chl-a concentrations cannot be measured when TCC is too high. Therefore, these results do not represent the true relationship of TCC and chl-a but they clearly show the negative character of the relationship. Results for the correlation with wind speed align with findings of Kahru et al. (2010) for the BaS who also found weak negative correlations. But the results deviate slightly from their findings in the NoS, where they found weak positive correlations. Wind may push phytoplankton out of the euphotic zone. Thus, it may limit growth which would explain the weak negative correlation during the summer months, that is found for both seas in this study.

In contrast to TCC and wind speed, SST displayed correlations on a big range and high variability. Correlations were predominantly negative in the NoS and positive in the BaS. For some regions big inter-monthly leaps were calculated. This shows that the relationship between chl-a and SST is far more complex than between chl-a and the other two parameters.

Temperature has complex direct and indirect impacts on phytoplankton. It influences the stratification and mixing of the water body, the activity of predators and the physiological rate of the phytoplankton itself, like enzymatic reactions. Non-linear responses of phytoplankton to changes in temperature are documented and are linked to “predator-prey interactions, resource limitation and community species composition” (Guinder and Molinero, 2013). The results of this work show that the relationship between chl-a and therefore, phytoplankton and SST may differ strongly on temporal and spatial scales. Striking differences between NoS and BaS as well as between the eight focus regions were found. In a single region, relationships may change from a negative to a positive relationship or vice versa in the course of a month (for example, Forties and Viking between April and May).

Most outstanding is the opposite inclination of the relationship in the two seas. Tilzer et al. (1986) point out that temperature has no impact on light-limited rates of photosynthesis but light-saturated

rates increase with temperature. This may explain the relatively strong positive correlation in June, July and August in the BaS. But in the NoS, negative relationships prevail the whole year and are lowest in the months with the most light (May, June, July). A possible reason for this difference could be the strong eutrophication of the BaS, which provides nutrients to phytoplankton at all times, even when the water body is stratified. Another reason might be the abundance of cyanobacteria which is witnessed in the BaS in summer. Paerl & Huisman (2008) have pointed out that cyanobacteria blooms are favored by high temperatures. They also profit from water stratification as it helps them to form dense surface blooms. This would explain the strong positive relationship between chl-a concentrations and SST in the BaS summer. In contrast, NoS phytoplankton does not seem to profit from high SST in summer. Temperature increase can only lead to increased growth rates when resources are sufficient (Padilla-Gamiño & Carpenter, 2007). Since nutrient levels are much lower in the NoS, a strong stratification caused by high temperatures might lead to a quicker limitation of nutrients and therefore, a limitation of phytoplankton growth. Additionally, cyanobacteria are much rarer in the NoS than in the BaS. Warmer SST might also promote zooplankton activity which in turn decreases phytoplankton populations (Sommer & Lewandowska, 2011; Winder et al., 2012).

6.3 Properties and trends of the spring bloom

This work provides a large-scale view on the spring bloom properties in the NoS and BaS, which is presented in detail in Sec 5.3. While there are many studies describing the spring bloom phenomena in the BaS (e.g. Groetsch et al., 2016; Kahru et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2017), there is little material on the NoS, especially for the pelagic zone. This study offers new insights into the properties and changes of the spring bloom in the NoS and additional information on the BaS.

Findings are largely consistent with the literature. They show lower chl-a concentrations in spring in the NoS than in the BaS. A North-South gradient was found for the bloom start with earlier starts in the south in both seas (with some exceptions), which Zhang et al. (2017) and Groetsch et al. (2016) have also found for the BaS. NoS regions close to the BaS outlet also witness earlier starts, which is in agreement with Müller (2010). On average longer blooms occur in the NoS than in the BaS, while the BaS spring blooms have greater peak values and greater bloom sums.

Few significant changes have been found for the spring bloom in the study region. Most striking is the predominantly negative trend for the start of the spring bloom for both seas, indicating an earlier

bloom onset. This trend was significant in both English Channel sea regions as well as in the five biggest BaS regions (Southern BaS, Southeastern BaS, Central BaS, Northern BaS and Gulf of Riga). These results are supported by Kahru et al. (2016) who have found an earlier beginning of spring blooms in the BaS as well. Mixed and mostly insignificant trends were found for the end and length of the spring bloom, which do not allow conclusions. Groetsch et al. (2016) on the other hand, have found positive trends in spring bloom length in the BaS.

The trends of peak value and bloom sum are insignificant in the majority of the NoS, too. But almost completely positive trends (with one exception) were found for peak value and bloom sum in the BaS and two NoS regions closely connected to BaS waters (Skagerrak and Utsire). These positive trends were significant for four regions regarding peak value and three regions regarding bloom sum. This indicates that there is a weak increase in the spring bloom magnitude. These results are supported by Jaanus et al. (2011) who have found increased phytoplankton productivity for selected BaS regions and Kahru et al. (2016) who have found increased chl-a concentrations. Again, the results are contradicted by Groetsch et al. (2016) who have found a negative trend in peak values during the spring bloom.

While no clear trends were found for bloom properties in the NoS in this study, inconclusive results on the topic are found in the literature. Though nutrient concentrations decreased in the NoS, McQuatters-Gollop et al. (2007) have found increased chl-a concentrations which they connect to clearer water and climate variability. On the other hand, Capuzzo et al. (2018) found declining primary production which, according to them, are connected to decreasing chl-a.

While comparing the results of this work to the results of others, it has to be pointed out that no universal definition exists on what constitutes a bloom event. There are a variety of approaches to detect and analyze blooms in the literature which makes it difficult to compare results.

The trend towards an earlier start of the spring bloom is likely connected to the earlier onset of spring and higher temperatures caused by climate change (Feehan, Harley, & Minnen, 2009; Kahru et al., 2016). It is more difficult to find causes for positive trends for bloom sum and peak value in the BaS. Kahru et al. (2016) connect this trend to climate change and eutrophication but the exact mechanisms are yet not understood.

The measured timing and magnitude of the detected blooms depend strongly on the bloom threshold. Fleming & Kaitala (2006) used a fixed threshold which was tested in this work, but produced unsatisfying results. Due to the strong annual variability of chl-a, fixed thresholds of different values led to extreme misclassifications. There could be periods where several consecutive

months were classified as a bloom while in some low-chl-a years, no bloom was detected at all. The variable threshold used in this work is therefore the better choice but it could be optimized. The threshold was based on chl-a values of the period from 1st of February until 31st of October. Groetsch et al. (2016) were using a threshold that depends on only the spring bloom period (DOY 31 to 160). It should be tested if this approach yields better results.

6.4 Properties and trends of MHW

This work is the first to study MHW in marginal seas, specifically in the NoS and BaS. It was found that MHW do occur all over the study region at any time of the year and display a high variability regarding their length and intensity.

On average, the BaS has longer MHW with a higher I_{mean} and I_{max} than the NoS. But more strong, severe and extreme MHW occurred in the NoS. The frequency of moderate and strong MHW was higher in the BaS but the frequency of severe and extreme MHW higher in the NoS. MHW occur during every month of the year. On

average, most MHW days occur in June, July and September. The results show a distinct low in MHW days during spring. Especially, the BaS has its minimum in April. A similar low for I_{max} in spring was found in both seas with the exception of the English Channel and the Southern NoS, where I_{max} is almost equally distributed over the year.

There seems to be a physical process during spring which prevents the development of MHW. A possible explanation would be wind forcing but as can be seen in Fig. 33, wind speeds are relatively low in the BaS during April. Another reason might be increased river runoff during spring which distributes cold waters into the sea. Testing the mechanics behind the phenomena is beyond the scope of this thesis. Future research on MHW should integrate regional climate system modelling to understand the processes that cause and sustain these events. The fact that the spring low in I_{max} is not apparent in the southwestern part of the NoS indicates that these seasonal properties are not a

Figure 33: Mean monthly wind speed in the BaS focus regions.

global phenomena. They might be connected to factors that are present in marginal seas but not in the Atlantic.

Trend analysis shows a significant increasing trend of SST for the whole study region which is consistent with rising temperatures in the global oceans (Oliver et al., 2018). There is a North-South gradient for the slope of the trend in the BaS with a slower increase in the South and a faster increase in the North. The increase is more uniform in the NoS. On average, the temperature rises faster in the BaS than in the NoS.

The results show an increasing trend in MHW frequency for the whole study region which was significant in five out of twenty sea regions. Here, a North-South gradient in the BaS for the increase in frequency could be found, too (lower increase in the South, higher in the North). Hence, a correlation between increasing MHW frequency and rising SST can be assumed. The trend for I_{\max} is mostly negative over the whole study region, but only one of these negative trends is significant. The trend results for duration are mixed, weak and insignificant. These findings indicate that there is a positive trend in MHW frequency. There might also be a decrease in MHW intensity but more evidence has to be gathered. No trend could be found for duration of MHW with the exception of the two English Channel regions, which display a positive significant trend.

Findings for positive changes in frequency align with the results of Oliver et al. (2018) who found a 34% global increase. But they have also found a 17% increase in duration which is not reflected in the results for NoS or BaS. Only in the English Channel was an increase found. This might be an indicator that the global changes in duration may be driven by processes that predominate in oceans but not in marginal seas.

Differences in the findings for duration might also be caused by the short baseline period, that was used in this study. Hobday et al. (2016) recommend a baseline period of at least 30 years. This study only had 29 years at hand (1990 - 2018) while Oliver et al. (2018) examined 92 years (1925 - 2016). Hence, the threshold in this work is higher due to increase in temperature during the past decades. A longer baseline period and, thus, a lower threshold would lead to the detection of more and longer MHW. Future research might find more conclusive results by looking at a longer time series.

Oliver et al. (2018) have found a weak and insignificant increase in intensity. It would be interesting to know if decreasing trends in I_{\max} may also be found elsewhere or just in the study region.

6.5 Relationship between MHW and the spring bloom

Different relationships were found for MHW that occurred before (pre-bloom phase) and MHW that occurred during the bloom (bloom phase). No clear relationship is apparent for the pre-bloom phase. However, when MHW and spring blooms co-occurred there was positive relationship between the bloom indices of magnitude and MHW indices. There is lower frequency of MHW during the time of spring bloom than during the rest of the year which resulted in a relatively small sample size.

Pre-bloom Phase

In the NoS, there were significant correlations between increasing I_{\max} and an earlier spring bloom start, an earlier end and a shorter duration. This could indicate that the MHW occurring in the months before a bloom shorten the bloom event and shift it later into the year. On the other hand, weak and insignificant correlations were found for the number of MHW days during the pre-bloom phase which do not support this theory. In the BaS, an increasing number of MHW days during the pre-bloom phase correlated with a shorter length, a smaller peak value and a smaller chlorophyll sum. This could point towards a negative relationship between MHW during the pre-bloom phase and the magnitude of spring blooms in the BaS. But again, the correlations are weak and insignificant for the same bloom indices and I_{\max} . Subsequently, the results do not present enough evidence that allows for a conclusion on the relationship between MHW and spring bloom events during the pre-bloom phase.

Bloom Phase

Conflicting results were found for the relationship between the start and end of the bloom events and the MHW indices. For the start, a significant positive correlation was found for I_{\max} , a significant negative one for number of MHW days during the bloom phase. The same pattern was found in the BaS (with the only difference that the relationship between days and start was insignificant). For the bloom end and I_{\max} , relatively strong positive correlations were found in both seas. Yet, for end and number of days, the correlations were very weak and insignificant.

It is probable that these results are caused by the seasonal distribution of MHW days and I_{\max} as MHW are least likely to occur during spring over the whole study region (Fig. 30 and 31). Additionally, the mean I_{\max} is very low in spring, especially in April, but increases strongly in the

following month (Fig. 25). Thus, blooms that start and end later are more likely to co-occur with MHW of high intensity. This is especially the case for the BaS. Since there is a big difference between mean I_{\max} in winter and early spring (low I_{\max}) and summer and late spring (high I_{\max}), later ends are more likely to co-occur with MHW of high I_{\max} . The difference in number of MHW days before and after the bloom is not so big. Therefore, there is not such a strong positive correlation between number of days and bloom end. At the same time, earlier starts (negative correlations) are more likely to co-occur with higher number of MHW days. Thus, this work could not find a clear relationship between MHW and temporal bloom indices.

However, positive correlations were found for both MHW indices and the bloom indices of magnitude. These were predominantly significant and stronger in the NoS than in the BaS. This is strong evidence that there is a positive relationship of co-occurring MHW and bloom events. It has to be pointed out, that the correlations between number of MHW days and bloom indices are in most cases a few point stronger than the correlations between I_{\max} and the bloom indices.

There seems to be a positive influence of MHW on bloom magnitude or vice versa. Even a scenario of positive feedback as described by Dickey & Falkowski (2005) is possible: warmer temperatures create stable conditions in the upper sea layer which supports the plankton bloom. The bloom increases the sea surface warming which again leads to longer and more intense MHW. Yet, the relationship between the MHW and bloom indices is not linear (Fig. 29), showing that other factors play an important role in the formation and sustainment of blooms and MHW. This positive relationship is conclusive with the literature describing the positive effect of phytoplankton on the surface layer heat budget (e.g. Dickey & Falkowski, 2005; Stramska & Dickey, 1993; Timmermann & Jin, 2002; Wetzel et al., 2006).

While co-occurring MHW and blooms seem to have a positive relationship, the low number of MHW days during the spring bloom, especially in the BaS cannot be ignored. It is likely that this is not related to the peak in chl-a concentration but to geophysical processes which cannot be detected in this study. Further investigation are necessary to find the cause.

The results of this work disagree with other research, which has found a decrease in biomass during mesocosm experiments applying high temperature treatments (Remy, Hillebrand, and Flöder, 2017; Sommer and Lengfellner, 2008; Sommer and Lewandowska, 2011; Stefanidou et al., 2018) Yet, the findings presented here do not indicate that MHW have a negative effect on phytoplankton biomass. It is hard to compare these results, as mesocosm experiments are limited to few environmental factors and species while the real world processes are very complex. Additionally, some of these

experiments worked with very strong temperature increases. For example, Stefanidou et al. (2018) increased the temperature by 6 °C over three days. Such an extreme increase is rare in the data sample of this work. It is also possible that MHW have a negative effect on some species, while other species thrive, thus, filling an ecological gap. More research needs to be done to find out what happens on the species level during MHW.

According to the definition of Smith (2011), an ecological extreme event is an event, that should “alter ecosystem structure and/or function well outside the bounds of what is considered typical or normal variability”. The MHW detected in this study did not have such effects on the phytoplankton phenology. Thus, when regarding the phytoplankton spring bloom, the MHW in the BaS and NoS are extreme events merely in a climatological but not in an ecological sense. Again it has to be pointed out though, that it is unknown what happened during the MHW on the species level. Some of the MHW might have had extreme effects on certain phytoplankton species.

Due to the low of MHW in spring and the relatively short sampling time of 25 years there are not many spring blooms that co-occurred with MHW. In many regions, there are not enough co-occurring events to calculate correlations. For this reason, events were summarized for A) all NoS regions and B) all BaS regions. This prohibited an exclusive look on the marine sea regions. Thus, the influence of the different biogeochemical and physical properties of the regions could not be examined.

The findings might also be biased by the fact that stratification caused by high temperatures may lead to surface accumulation of phytoplankton which in turn leads to too high remotely sensed measurements (Groetsch et al., 2014)

Because the majority of spring blooms did not witness an MHW, the sample was limited to the ones that did. When repeating the analysis with all spring blooms, including the ones without MHW (in which cases the index for MHW days would be 0 and the index for I_{\max} would be negative) for the bloom phase, weaker but significant correlations of the same relationship direction were found, as can be seen in Tab. 9. Especially in the case of I_{\max} , this shows that the relationship between SST and blooms is not linear but changes with increasing temperatures.

This study also looked at the relationship of MHW that occurred before a bloom but only included a time period of 30 days prior to the event. Pitarch et al. (2016) stated that a warm winter in 2007/2008 triggered a spring bloom of high magnitude in 2008. Said bloom event has also been found in this study. It followed a long MHW in the previous winter. Therefore, future research should look at the influence of MHW during winter time.

Table 9: Spearman's correlations between MHW indices (I_{\max} , number of days) and bloom indices for all blooms and only blooms co-occurring with MHW.

	North Sea		Baltic Sea	
	MHW I_{\max}	No. of MHW days	MHW I_{\max}	No. of MHW days
All blooms				
Bloom start	-0,01	-0,07	0,10	-0,02
Bloom end	0,20	0,04	0,32	0,18
Bloom length	0,35	0,19	0,38	0,31
Bloom peak value	0,13	0,15	0,23	0,18
Bloom sum	0,27	0,22	0,38	0,33
Only blooms co-occurring with MHW				
Bloom start	0,27	-0,27	0,55	-0,26
Bloom end	0,58	0,07	0,73	0,10
Bloom length	0,43	0,49	0,34	0,40
Bloom peak value	0,52	0,51	0,17	0,16
Bloom sum	0,54	0,61	0,35	0,34

7 Conclusion

This chapter offers a summary of the motivation, methods and results of this work and provides an outlook to possible future research.

7.1 Summary

Climate change has grave impacts on marine environments. One consequence of the changing climate is the increase of extreme heat events, so called MHW. While it has been shown that there is a growing trend for frequency and duration of MHW in the global oceans (Oliver et al., 2018), there is yet no knowledge on the properties of MHW in the NoS and BaS. MHW can have severe and destructive consequences on marine species, ecosystems and biogeochemical processes (Smale et al., 2019). So far, there is little research on the impacts of MHW on phytoplankton. Most of it is limited to mesocosm experiments and, to the knowledge of the author, there are no approaches applying remotely sensed data.

This thesis aimed to show that SST and MHW are meaningful parameters for the phytoplankton spring bloom and to find out if there is a relationship between co-occurring MHW and bloom events. It also aimed to describe properties and changes of MHW and spring blooms in the NoS and BaS.

To achieve this, remotely sensed daily raster data of SST, chl-a, TCC and wind speed were used to calculate daily means for twenty marine sea regions. Monthly correlations between chl-a and respectively SST, TCC and wind speed were calculated and compared. MHW were detected and categorized using the methods provided by Hobday et al. (2016, 2018). Spring bloom events were detected using a threshold method. Event indices were calculated for both event types and the Mann-Kendall trend test was applied to analyze changes in event indices as well as SST. Finally, Spearman's correlation coefficients were calculated for MHW indices and bloom indices in two cases: 1. For blooms and MHW occurring in the thirty days before the bloom event. 2. For blooms and MHW occurring at the same time.

This work is limited by general issues associated with the remote sensing of chl-a concentrations like missing data due to cloud cover and uncertainties regarding the vertical distribution of phytoplankton. Remote sensing is especially complicated in the BaS due to high concentrations of CDOM and cyanobacteria. While validation of the OC-CCI data with in situ data

exists for the BaS (Hieronymi et al., 2015), no such validation has been done for the NoS. Therefore, these results do not present absolute values but only indicators for trends and relationships.

Since a raster based approach would have been beyond the scope of this thesis, regional means had to be calculated. Thus, processes and patterns on small spatial scales are not reflected in this work. The results of MHW and bloom detection also highly depend on the selected regions used for averaging and will differ when choosing different partitioning. No universal definition exists on what constitutes a bloom event and differing approaches can be found all over the literature. This makes it difficult to compare results. When choosing a threshold based approach, like in this work, results depend highly on the type of threshold picked. Finally, the period of the SST time series in use was only 29 years long while Hobday et al. (2016) recommend at least 30 years.

Despite these limitations this work provides an overview on developments of spring bloom, SST and MHW in the NoS and BaS and successfully examined the relationship of co-occurring MHW and bloom events.

It was found that compared to the two other meteorological parameters (TCC and wind speed), the relationship between SST and chl-a concentrations is far more complex. Higher correlation maxima and inter monthly changes of relationship direction were found. Relationships changed strongly depending on the sea region and the month. The relationships also had opposing directions in the two seas: mainly negative in the NoS and mainly positive in the BaS. This is likely connected to different biogeochemical regimes, different nutrient concentrations and different species compositions in both seas.

This thesis gives a detailed insight into the properties of timing and magnitude of the spring bloom in the study region. The findings are mostly in agreement with existing research on the spring bloom in the BaS. They offer new information on the pelagic zone of the NoS, where the spring bloom has mostly been studied in coastal areas. Results show, among other things, that blooms have a higher peak value and higher sum in the BaS but are longer in the NoS. A decreasing gradient from West to East was found regarding mean chl-a concentrations. For the mean bloom start, a North-South gradient was found for both seas with earlier bloom offsets in the south.

During the last 20 years, a trend towards an earlier spring bloom start has developed which is significantly stronger in the BaS. No clear trend was found for the end of the spring bloom season and the length of blooms in both seas. Also, no trend was found for the peak value and bloom sum in the NoS. There is indication for a positive trend in bloom sum and peak value and therefore in

bloom magnitude in the BaS but the evidence is still too thin to draw a definite conclusion. These trends in the BaS have also been found by others and might likely be connected to climate variability and eutrophication (Jaanus et al., 2011; Kahru et al., 2016).

MHW in the BaS and NoS were successfully detected and described for the first time. It was found that MHW occur all over the study region and show high variability in length and intensity. MHW in the BaS are on average longer and more intense than in the NoS. Yet, the NoS witnesses more MHW of higher categories (meaning MHW with very high I_{max}). The trend analysis shows an overall significant increase in SST which is stronger in the BaS than in the NoS and which is associated with a faster increase in the North than in the South. There is a growing trend in MHW frequency, which is in alignment with the findings of Oliver et al. (2018). But Oliver and others also found an increase in duration which is not present in the results of this work. A predominant negative but insignificant trend in I_{max} was found in the study region. Results show a low point of MHW days and MHW intensity during spring which is especially obvious in the BaS regions.

No clear relationship was found between MHW occurring in the month before a bloom event and the bloom. But significant positive relationships were found for MHW indices and bloom indices of magnitude (sum, peak value and length) regarding MHW and blooms occurring at the same time. These positive relationships are present in both seas but stronger in the NoS than in the BaS. They indicate that one event might have an enhancing effect on the other or that a situation of positive feedback is created. These results support the findings from other literature (e.g. Dickey and Falkowski, 2005; Kahru, Leppanen, and Rud, 1993; Lewis, Cullen, and Platt, 1983; Lewis, Kuring, and Yentsch, 1988)

7.2 Outlook

Research on MHW is fairly new and has so far concentrated on global oceans. This work was the first to apply the MHW detection method provided by Hobday et al. (2016) on a smaller, regional scale. To understand the mechanics of MHW, more small, regional scale studies on coastal areas or marginal seas should be done. This study was limited by a short time series. The application of a longer time series could offer better results for the NoS, BaS and other regions.

A striking phenomena found in the course of this study was the low point of MHW days and MHW intensity during spring. To understand and explain this, more research on the processes that form and sustain MHW is necessary.

The MHW definition provided by Hobday et al. (2016) made it relatively easy to detect MHW and compare the findings to results in the literature. Such a universal definition is lacking for phytoplankton blooms. Future research should focus on finding a definition and an all-purpose method to detect and analyze blooms.

It is recommended that future research includes the application of the methods of MHW and bloom detection and index analysis to raster data. This would make the evaluation of small spatial patterns and processes possible. When regional means have to be calculated, partitioning should be based on the biogeochemical properties of the sea regions in order to avoid covering more than one ecological province (Platt & Sathyendranath, 2008). More advanced interpolation methods like DINEOF should be considered when interpolating daily remote sensing data.

Remote-sensing of phytoplankton remains a challenge, especially in the BaS. Algorithms better adapted to the conditions in the BaS are needed to perform chl-a concentration analysis. This would also make it possible to study the relationship of MHW and summer blooms in the BaS.

The findings of this work were limited to a small sampling size due to the low-point in MHW days during spring. An analysis of the relationship during summer bloom could offer more insight. Nonetheless, the relationship of co-occurring spring blooms and MHW is clearly positive and future research should try to analyze the associated processes in detail. The key question is, if blooms reinforce MHW, if MHW reinforce blooms or if there is positive feedback between the two. It is also critical to put a focus on the relationship of MHW and HAB as these might “feed” each other when occurring at the same time, thus, putting enormous stress on marine ecosystems. In this context, coupled ocean biogeochemical model studies could play a role in further understanding the complex relationship between MHW and phytoplankton blooms.

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1. Engl. Channel West					2. Engl. Channel East				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1994-07-31	"II Strong"	3.02	7	1	1994-07-29	"II Strong"	2.34	9
2	1994-11-30	"I Moderate"	1.57	8	2	1994-08-23	"I Moderate"	1.51	6
3	1995-02-07	"I Moderate"	1.73	12	3	1994-11-30	"I Moderate"	2.25	8
4	1995-02-24	"I Moderate"	1.85	8	4	1994-12-18	"I Moderate"	2.29	7
5	1995-08-19	"I Moderate"	1.81	5	5	1994-12-29	"I Moderate"	2.31	17
6	1997-08-13	"II Strong"	2.19	6	6	1995-02-14	"I Moderate"	1.92	9
7	1997-11-19	"I Moderate"	1.36	5	7	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	2.11	5
8	2003-08-08	"II Strong"	2.14	6	8	1998-01-13	"I Moderate"	1.73	5
9	2005-07-13	"II Strong"	3.27	5	9	1999-09-22	"I Moderate"	1.37	5
10	2006-07-24	"I Moderate"	1.96	5	10	2005-10-26	"I Moderate"	1.87	11
11	2006-11-13	"I Moderate"	1.96	7	11	2006-10-30	"I Moderate"	1.56	6
12	2006-12-24	"I Moderate"	2.06	5	12	2007-01-19	"I Moderate"	2.24	5
13	2007-01-19	"I Moderate"	2.35	5	13	2007-02-23	"I Moderate"	2.35	27
14	2007-02-04	"I Moderate"	2.22	8	14	2007-04-22	"II Strong"	2.7	5
15	2007-02-20	"II Strong"	2.29	20	15	2007-05-22	"I Moderate"	2	7
16	2007-03-18	"I Moderate"	1.94	14	16	2014-01-15	"I Moderate"	2.06	9
17	2007-04-08	"I Moderate"	1.61	7	17	2014-02-18	"I Moderate"	1.82	8
18	2014-04-08	"I Moderate"	1.56	8	18	2014-03-01	"I Moderate"	2.21	5
19	2014-05-14	"II Strong"	2.24	7	19	2014-03-15	"I Moderate"	2.05	7
20	2014-06-11	"I Moderate"	2.21	5	20	2014-04-04	"I Moderate"	2.17	12
21	2014-06-19	"II Strong"	2.59	9	21	2014-05-11	"I Moderate"	2.05	29
22	2014-07-19	"II Strong"	2.66	21	22	2014-05-24	"I Moderate"	1.74	10
23	2014-09-06	"I Moderate"	1.42	5	23	2014-06-06	"II Strong"	2.25	9
24	2014-09-28	"II Strong"	2.46	8	24	2014-06-23	"I Moderate"	1.79	5
25	2014-11-03	"I Moderate"	1.98	8	25	2014-07-18	"I Moderate"	2.02	27
26	2014-11-26	"I Moderate"	1.75	11	26	2014-09-18	"II Strong"	2.29	36
27	2014-12-28	"I Moderate"	1.43	5	27	2014-10-27	"I Moderate"	2.03	24
28	2015-12-19	"I Moderate"	1.89	7	28	2014-11-28	"II Strong"	2.77	25
29	2015-12-29	"I Moderate"	2.3	19	29	2015-12-27	"I Moderate"	2.32	6
30	2016-02-06	"I Moderate"	2.15	13	30	2016-02-07	"I Moderate"	1.46	5
31	2016-09-06	"II Strong"	2.13	12	31	2016-08-23	"II Strong"	2.46	25
32	2017-04-04	"I Moderate"	1.77	27	32	2016-09-07	"I Moderate"	1.98	31

33	2017-05-24	"II Strong"	2.41	12	33	2017-03-29	"II Strong"	2.75	23
34	2017-06-17	"II Strong"	3.29	11	34	2017-05-15	"III Severe"	3.43	42
35	2017-07-04	"I Moderate"	2.59	7	35	2017-06-10	"I Moderate"	2.15	15
36	2018-07-05	"II Strong"	3.01	13	36	2018-07-01	"I Moderate"	1.97	16
					37	2018-07-31	"I Moderate"	1.16	5
					38	2018-10-14	"I Moderate"	1.71	13
3. Southwestern North Sea					4. Dogger				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1994-07-24	"II Strong"	3.45	21	1	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	3.05	8
2	1994-12-01	"I Moderate"	2.75	6	2	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	4.28	27
3	1995-08-16	"II Strong"	3.33	11	3	1995-08-15	"II Strong"	3.69	13
4	1995-11-12	"I Moderate"	2.05	5	4	1995-09-16	"I Moderate"	1.79	6
5	1997-08-15	"I Moderate"	2.12	7	5	1997-08-12	"II Strong"	4.03	16
6	1998-04-02	"I Moderate"	1.67	5	6	1999-07-06	"I Moderate"	2.57	6
7	2003-09-20	"I Moderate"	1.9	6	7	1999-09-22	"I Moderate"	1.88	9
8	2006-07-25	"I Moderate"	2.53	5	8	2002-08-15	"I Moderate"	2.4	6
9	2006-09-29	"I Moderate"	1.94	7	9	2002-08-26	"I Moderate"	2.45	5
10	2006-10-10	"I Moderate"	2.4	8	10	2003-05-29	"II Strong"	3.93	21
11	2007-01-17	"I Moderate"	2.67	7	11	2003-08-08	"I Moderate"	3.03	6
12	2007-02-28	"I Moderate"	2.33	20	12	2003-09-19	"I Moderate"	2.36	6
13	2007-04-18	"II Strong"	2.77	17	13	2005-10-28	"I Moderate"	2.03	9
14	2007-06-06	"II Strong"	3.34	6	14	2006-07-04	"I Moderate"	2.87	5
15	2014-01-31	"II Strong"	3.07	58	15	2006-07-21	"II Strong"	4.33	13
16	2014-04-07	"II Strong"	3.01	33	16	2006-09-26	"II Strong"	2.78	32
17	2014-05-15	"I Moderate"	2.2	6	17	2007-01-16	"I Moderate"	1.57	10
18	2014-06-05	"I Moderate"	2.6	12	18	2007-01-31	"I Moderate"	1.33	6
19	2014-06-20	"I Moderate"	1.96	6	19	2007-02-28	"I Moderate"	1.59	12
20	2014-06-30	"I Moderate"	2.56	7	20	2007-03-16	"I Moderate"	1.63	6
21	2014-07-22	"I Moderate"	2.7	18	21	2007-04-13	"I Moderate"	2.14	9
22	2014-09-16	"I Moderate"	2.09	5	22	2007-04-25	"I Moderate"	1.82	7
23	2014-09-30	"I Moderate"	2.06	6	23	2008-05-10	"II Strong"	3.44	8
24	2014-11-24	"II Strong"	2.88	7	24	2008-06-06	"II Strong"	3.25	5
25	2015-12-27	"II Strong"	3.65	28	25	2009-06-29	"II Strong"	3.24	10
26	2016-02-07	"I Moderate"	2.4	7	26	2010-05-20	"I Moderate"	2.53	5
27	2016-08-28	"I Moderate"	1.7	5	27	2011-04-16	"I Moderate"	1.82	11
28	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.46	29	28	2011-11-23	"II Strong"	2.67	6
29	2017-04-02	"I Moderate"	2.42	14	29	2012-03-25	"I Moderate"	1.81	6
30	2017-06-17	"II Strong"	3.85	8	30	2014-02-24	"I Moderate"	1.31	7

31	2017-07-02	"II Strong"	3.18	10	31	2014-03-20	"I Moderate"	1.59	5
32	2018-05-30	"I Moderate"	2.46	6	32	2014-05-16	"I Moderate"	2.45	6
33	2018-07-31	"II Strong"	4.03	11	33	2014-06-06	"II Strong"	3.13	11
					34	2014-07-23	"I Moderate"	3.42	15
					35	2014-11-17	"II Strong"	2.68	10
					36	2014-12-02	"I Moderate"	1.86	10
					37	2015-01-04	"I Moderate"	1.64	5
					38	2015-11-03	"II Strong"	2.63	8
					39	2015-12-20	"I Moderate"	1.7	6
					40	2016-01-25	"I Moderate"	1.93	22
					41	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.26	23
					42	2016-12-21	"I Moderate"	1.13	7
					43	2017-04-06	"I Moderate"	1.84	7
					44	2018-05-30	"II Strong"	4.12	5
					45	2018-07-02	"I Moderate"	2.92	7
					46	2018-07-17	"I Moderate"	3.53	8
5. Forties					66. Viking				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-05-03	"I Moderate"	2.4	10	1	1992-05-26	"II Strong"	3.97	9
2	1994-07-06	"II Strong"	3.33	34	2	1992-06-07	"II Strong"	3.23	6
3	1995-08-15	"II Strong"	3.99	11	3	1994-07-29	"I Moderate"	2.74	9
4	1995-09-15	"I Moderate"	2.44	8	4	1995-09-18	"I Moderate"	1.95	6
5	1997-08-12	"II Strong"	4.53	25	5	1997-08-12	"II Strong"	4.1	29
6	1998-02-25	"I Moderate"	1.57	8	6	1998-02-26	"I Moderate"	1.53	6
7	1999-07-07	"I Moderate"	2.21	7	7	1998-04-03	"I Moderate"	1.34	5
8	2002-08-07	"I Moderate"	2.54	6	8	2000-05-11	"I Moderate"	2.11	6
9	2002-08-26	"I Moderate"	2.41	5	9	2002-06-12	"I Moderate"	2.46	5
10	2002-09-19	"I Moderate"	1.85	5	10	2002-08-04	"I Moderate"	3.3	7
11	2002-09-29	"I Moderate"	2.04	13	11	2002-08-22	"II Strong"	3.09	10
12	2003-06-05	"I Moderate"	3.01	15	12	2002-09-07	"II Strong"	2.91	30
13	2003-07-19	"I Moderate"	2.31	5	13	2003-07-15	"II Strong"	3.35	11
14	2003-08-07	"I Moderate"	3.08	7	14	2003-08-06	"I Moderate"	2.7	5
15	2006-07-21	"I Moderate"	4.06	14	15	2004-01-21	"I Moderate"	1.36	5
16	2006-09-26	"I Moderate"	2.38	13	16	2006-07-21	"II Strong"	4.18	14
17	2006-10-13	"III Severe"	3.09	19	17	2006-08-16	"II Strong"	3.93	14
18	2006-12-30	"I Moderate"	1.36	5	18	2006-09-26	"II Strong"	2.22	32
19	2007-01-12	"I Moderate"	1.43	30	19	2006-12-27	"I Moderate"	1.4	12
20	2007-02-28	"I Moderate"	1.36	19	20	2007-01-16	"I Moderate"	1.23	5

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21	2007-04-11	"II Strong"	2.03	8	21	2007-02-16	"II Strong"	1.85	5
22	2007-04-27	"I Moderate"	1.89	5	22	2008-05-08	"II Strong"	2.29	8
23	2007-06-21	"I Moderate"	2.54	5	23	2008-06-02	"II Strong"	3.85	8
24	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	3.34	7	24	2009-06-25	"IV Extreme"	6.03	13
25	2008-05-21	"I Moderate"	1.82	6	25	2011-04-25	"II Strong"	1.98	13
26	2008-06-03	"II Strong"	3.57	8	26	2014-06-04	"II Strong"	3.95	10
27	2009-06-28	"II Strong"	4.66	11	27	2014-07-21	"II Strong"	4.98	20
28	2011-04-28	"I Moderate"	1.64	7	28	2014-09-16	"I Moderate"	1.99	14
29	2014-05-17	"I Moderate"	2.5	5	29	2014-11-20	"I Moderate"	1.53	6
30	2014-06-06	"I Moderate"	3.15	13	30	2014-12-05	"I Moderate"	1.09	5
31	2014-07-22	"II Strong"	4.15	15	31	2015-10-16	"II Strong"	2.08	44
32	2015-11-06	"II Strong"	1.92	9	32	2015-12-02	"I Moderate"	1.62	26
33	2015-12-20	"I Moderate"	1.45	6	33	2016-01-03	"I Moderate"	1.26	5
34	2016-09-12	"I Moderate"	2.6	14	34	2016-12-17	"I Moderate"	1.26	7
35	2016-10-27	"I Moderate"	1.57	6	35	2016-12-31	"I Moderate"	1.49	6
36	2016-12-21	"I Moderate"	1.3	5	36	2017-01-18	"II Strong"	1.57	6
37	2018-05-28	"III Severe"	4.91	13	37	2017-02-02	"II Strong"	1.63	11
38	2018-07-15	"I Moderate"	3.61	10	38	2017-03-11	"I Moderate"	1.59	9
					39	2018-05-27	"III Severe"	5.55	13
					40	2018-07-18	"I Moderate"	2.93	7
7. Ijsselmeer					8. German Bight				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-05-04	"II Strong"	4.71	6	1	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	4.1	10
2	1994-06-30	"II Strong"	7.07	31	2	1994-07-06	"II Strong"	4.71	37
3	1994-08-02	"II Strong"	6.67	8	3	1995-08-16	"I Moderate"	2.65	11
4	1995-02-16	"I Moderate"	3.55	9	4	1997-08-13	"II Strong"	4.1	25
5	1995-08-16	"II Strong"	4.22	9	5	1999-09-11	"I Moderate"	2.18	20
6	1997-08-13	"II Strong"	5.52	9	6	2000-05-10	"II Strong"	3.99	7
7	1998-01-13	"I Moderate"	2.82	5	7	2002-02-11	"I Moderate"	2.12	6
8	1998-05-15	"I Moderate"	3.01	5	8	2002-08-16	"I Moderate"	3.1	33
9	1999-09-07	"II Strong"	4.1	7	9	2003-05-31	"I Moderate"	2.84	6
10	2000-05-09	"II Strong"	5.71	8	10	2003-08-08	"I Moderate"	3.13	7
11	2000-12-13	"II Strong"	4.8	7	11	2006-07-04	"I Moderate"	2.97	6
12	2001-08-24	"I Moderate"	3.93	5	12	2006-07-21	"I Moderate"	3.99	12
13	2001-10-30	"I Moderate"	3.09	7	13	2006-09-30	"I Moderate"	2.49	6
14	2001-12-04	"I Moderate"	2.72	6	14	2006-10-11	"I Moderate"	2.75	21
15	2002-02-10	"II Strong"	5.34	11	15	2006-12-05	"I Moderate"	2.63	6
16	2002-08-16	"I Moderate"	4.1	5	16	2007-01-09	"I Moderate"	3.04	16

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17	2003-06-01	"I Moderate"	4.69	9	17	2007-02-01	"I Moderate"	2.39	7
18	2003-08-10	"II Strong"	5.18	6	18	2007-02-28	"I Moderate"	2.86	23
19	2005-01-10	"I Moderate"	3.81	6	19	2007-03-28	"I Moderate"	3.41	39
20	2005-11-03	"I Moderate"	3.54	7	20	2007-06-05	"III Severe"	5.8	9
21	2006-07-03	"I Moderate"	3.72	6	21	2007-06-22	"I Moderate"	2.5	5
22	2006-07-19	"I Moderate"	5.21	13	22	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	4.21	7
23	2006-09-15	"I Moderate"	3.81	21	23	2008-06-07	"II Strong"	3.97	5
24	2006-10-22	"I Moderate"	3.1	8	24	2009-06-29	"I Moderate"	3.34	10
25	2006-11-26	"I Moderate"	2.92	5	25	2014-02-19	"I Moderate"	2.66	11
26	2006-12-16	"I Moderate"	3.42	5	26	2014-03-16	"I Moderate"	2.97	15
27	2007-01-19	"II Strong"	5.09	7	27	2014-04-05	"I Moderate"	2.86	9
28	2007-03-01	"I Moderate"	3.85	16	28	2014-04-22	"I Moderate"	3.2	10
29	2007-04-14	"I Moderate"	3.8	10	29	2014-06-06	"I Moderate"	3.3	10
30	2007-04-28	"I Moderate"	2.91	8	30	2014-07-10	"I Moderate"	2.43	5
31	2007-06-07	"II Strong"	4.95	7	31	2014-07-21	"I Moderate"	3.91	19
32	2008-05-07	"I Moderate"	3.93	6	32	2014-09-30	"I Moderate"	2.83	43
33	2009-04-13	"I Moderate"	2.95	13	33	2014-11-17	"I Moderate"	2.81	6
34	2009-06-29	"I Moderate"	3.97	8	34	2014-12-02	"II Strong"	3.34	5
35	2009-11-21	"I Moderate"	2.82	8	35	2015-11-08	"I Moderate"	2.85	15
36	2010-07-02	"I Moderate"	4.42	13	36	2015-12-27	"I Moderate"	3.3	6
37	2011-04-17	"I Moderate"	4.38	14	37	2016-02-07	"I Moderate"	2.58	7
38	2011-09-30	"I Moderate"	3.6	6	38	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.56	34
39	2012-03-21	"I Moderate"	3.49	8	39	2018-05-26	"III Severe"	6.08	18
40	2012-05-23	"I Moderate"	4.19	8	40	2018-07-30	"I Moderate"	3.52	11
41	2012-08-18	"I Moderate"	3.98	6					
42	2014-01-03	"I Moderate"	3.67	12					
43	2014-03-20	"I Moderate"	3.97	7					
44	2014-04-08	"I Moderate"	3.63	7					
45	2014-05-21	"I Moderate"	3.43	5					
46	2014-06-10	"I Moderate"	4.13	5					
47	2014-09-16	"I Moderate"	3.61	6					
48	2014-09-30	"I Moderate"	3.73	5					
49	2014-10-16	"I Moderate"	3.41	5					
50	2015-07-02	"II Strong"	5.78	5					
51	2015-12-28	"II Strong"	5.17	5					
52	2016-08-23	"II Strong"	4.21	10					
53	2016-09-05	"III Severe"	6.24	30					
54	2017-03-30	"I Moderate"	4.15	13					

55	2017-05-25	"I Moderate"	4.29	12					
56	2017-06-18	"II Strong"	4.9	5					
57	2018-04-18	"I Moderate"	3.93	6					
58	2018-05-25	"II Strong"	6.71	14					
59	2018-07-26	"II Strong"	5.75	15					
60	2018-10-14	"I Moderate"	4.09	9					
9. Fisher					10. Utsire				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-05-02	"II Strong"	4.59	11	1	1990-05-02	"II Strong"	3.81	11
2	1992-05-27	"I Moderate"	3.34	8	2	1992-05-25	"I Moderate"	4.57	20
3	1992-06-07	"I Moderate"	2.68	5	3	1994-07-21	"I Moderate"	3.87	16
4	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	4.44	33	4	1997-07-12	"I Moderate"	4.63	16
5	1997-07-22	"I Moderate"	3.67	5	5	1997-08-07	"II Strong"	5.43	34
6	1997-08-07	"II Strong"	4.93	35	6	1998-02-25	"I Moderate"	1.84	6
7	1999-07-09	"I Moderate"	3.15	6	7	1999-07-09	"I Moderate"	3.28	5
8	1999-09-21	"II Strong"	3.04	13	8	2001-07-06	"I Moderate"	3.07	5
9	2000-05-07	"II Strong"	4.17	11	9	2002-08-06	"II Strong"	4.4	26
10	2002-08-16	"II Strong"	4.05	21	10	2002-09-07	"II Strong"	2.93	18
11	2002-09-09	"I Moderate"	2.55	13	11	2002-09-30	"I Moderate"	1.87	8
12	2003-08-08	"I Moderate"	3.67	6	12	2003-07-14	"I Moderate"	3.51	6
13	2005-10-27	"I Moderate"	2.15	10	13	2003-08-07	"I Moderate"	3.91	6
14	2005-11-11	"I Moderate"	2.05	10	14	2004-08-11	"I Moderate"	3.37	5
15	2006-07-04	"II Strong"	3.64	5	15	2006-07-04	"I Moderate"	3.35	5
16	2006-07-22	"I Moderate"	3.71	16	16	2006-07-24	"I Moderate"	3.5	14
17	2006-08-24	"I Moderate"	2.72	6	17	2006-08-14	"I Moderate"	3.29	17
18	2006-09-27	"II Strong"	3.22	31	18	2006-09-27	"II Strong"	2.73	31
19	2006-12-30	"I Moderate"	2.43	41	19	2006-11-06	"I Moderate"	2.63	10
20	2007-03-29	"I Moderate"	1.68	10	20	2006-12-05	"I Moderate"	2.26	13
21	2007-04-11	"I Moderate"	2.37	8	21	2006-12-24	"I Moderate"	2.53	50
22	2007-04-26	"II Strong"	3.17	8	22	2007-06-07	"I Moderate"	4.28	6
23	2007-06-07	"II Strong"	5.47	6	23	2007-06-20	"I Moderate"	3.05	6
24	2007-06-21	"II Strong"	3.54	6	24	2008-05-04	"II Strong"	3.69	9
25	2008-02-24	"I Moderate"	1.76	5	25	2008-06-01	"II Strong"	4.82	9
26	2008-05-05	"II Strong"	4.65	14	26	2008-07-28	"I Moderate"	3.63	6
27	2008-05-22	"I Moderate"	2.16	5	27	2009-06-29	"II Strong"	5.19	9
28	2008-06-01	"II Strong"	4.79	10	28	2014-06-04	"I Moderate"	4.43	9
29	2009-06-29	"II Strong"	3.81	10	29	2014-07-20	"II Strong"	6.64	21
30	2014-03-16	"II Strong"	2.66	12	30	2014-09-11	"I Moderate"	1.97	12

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31	2014-04-07	"I Moderate"	1.83	6	31	2014-09-28	"I Moderate"	1.73	5
32	2014-06-06	"I Moderate"	3.67	11	32	2014-11-01	"I Moderate"	2.29	13
33	2014-07-10	"I Moderate"	3.38	5	33	2014-11-17	"I Moderate"	2.05	6
34	2014-07-21	"II Strong"	5.06	19	34	2014-12-12	"I Moderate"	2.16	9
35	2014-10-26	"III Severe"	4.06	15	35	2015-01-11	"I Moderate"	1.89	6
36	2014-11-17	"II Strong"	2.93	33	36	2015-12-06	"I Moderate"	2.02	10
37	2015-01-01	"I Moderate"	1.59	6	37	2015-12-20	"I Moderate"	2.31	9
38	2015-11-16	"I Moderate"	1.66	7	38	2016-04-11	"I Moderate"	1.23	6
39	2015-12-09	"I Moderate"	1.77	5	39	2016-09-13	"II Strong"	2.96	23
40	2015-12-20	"I Moderate"	1.86	6	40	2017-02-04	"I Moderate"	2.23	7
41	2016-02-07	"I Moderate"	1.55	5	41	2017-10-26	"I Moderate"	1.84	5
42	2016-06-03	"I Moderate"	3.84	5	42	2017-11-09	"I Moderate"	1.7	9
43	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.29	24	43	2018-05-22	"II Strong"	6.52	20
44	2018-05-25	"III Severe"	6.66	18					
45	2018-07-30	"I Moderate"	3.13	6					
11. Skagerrak					12. Kattegat				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-03-18	"I Moderate"	2.89	12	1	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	4.75	8
2	1990-05-01	"II Strong"	4.57	12	2	1994-07-20	"II Strong"	5.28	27
3	1992-05-27	"I Moderate"	4.74	16	3	1995-08-16	"I Moderate"	3.2	9
4	1994-07-25	"I Moderate"	4.32	21	4	1997-08-08	"II Strong"	5.32	34
5	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	2.96	8	5	1999-09-08	"I Moderate"	2.01	6
6	1997-07-11	"I Moderate"	3.07	7	6	1999-09-22	"I Moderate"	2.41	12
7	1997-07-21	"I Moderate"	3.87	7	7	2000-05-05	"I Moderate"	3.61	14
8	1997-08-06	"II Strong"	4.91	37	8	2002-02-10	"I Moderate"	3.02	10
9	1998-02-22	"I Moderate"	2.68	9	9	2002-08-21	"II Strong"	3.39	32
10	1999-07-10	"I Moderate"	4.1	5	10	2005-01-09	"I Moderate"	3.04	10
11	1999-09-25	"I Moderate"	2.57	7	11	2005-07-09	"I Moderate"	3.73	5
12	2000-05-06	"II Strong"	4.24	7	12	2005-11-09	"I Moderate"	2.55	5
13	2000-12-13	"I Moderate"	2.53	7	13	2006-07-03	"I Moderate"	4.23	7
14	2002-02-07	"I Moderate"	2.5	7	14	2006-07-26	"I Moderate"	3.72	5
15	2002-08-16	"II Strong"	4.06	36	15	2006-09-25	"I Moderate"	3.31	31
16	2003-07-14	"I Moderate"	2.98	5	16	2006-11-06	"II Strong"	4.31	95
17	2003-08-08	"I Moderate"	3.75	5	17	2007-03-26	"I Moderate"	2.72	12
18	2004-08-09	"I Moderate"	3.86	5	18	2007-04-12	"I Moderate"	2.77	7
19	2005-01-09	"I Moderate"	2.82	8	19	2007-06-07	"II Strong"	6.04	7
20	2005-11-02	"I Moderate"	3.03	15	20	2008-02-27	"I Moderate"	3.31	11
21	2006-07-03	"I Moderate"	4.08	6	21	2008-03-13	"I Moderate"	2.5	6

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22	2006-07-26	"I Moderate"	3.64	7	22	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	4.89	11
23	2006-08-23	"I Moderate"	2.5	6	23	2008-06-01	"I Moderate"	4.41	10
24	2006-09-25	"II Strong"	3.61	92	24	2009-04-14	"I Moderate"	2.69	5
25	2006-12-30	"II Strong"	4.27	41	25	2009-06-29	"II Strong"	5.18	9
26	2007-03-17	"I Moderate"	2.12	5	26	2011-11-30	"I Moderate"	2.67	7
27	2007-03-26	"I Moderate"	2.49	12	27	2014-01-10	"I Moderate"	2.77	5
28	2007-06-07	"II Strong"	5.79	7	28	2014-03-19	"I Moderate"	2.8	8
29	2008-02-04	"I Moderate"	2.36	6	29	2014-05-31	"I Moderate"	4.04	13
30	2008-02-22	"I Moderate"	2.95	26	30	2014-07-21	"I Moderate"	4.63	17
31	2008-05-05	"II Strong"	4.8	9	31	2014-10-18	"I Moderate"	2.72	5
32	2008-06-01	"II Strong"	5.53	9	32	2014-11-07	"I Moderate"	3.29	6
33	2008-07-27	"I Moderate"	3.43	6	33	2014-12-15	"I Moderate"	2.89	5
34	2009-06-29	"II Strong"	4.71	11	34	2015-01-11	"I Moderate"	2.75	8
35	2011-07-31	"I Moderate"	3.31	5	35	2015-11-11	"I Moderate"	2.58	9
36	2011-11-30	"I Moderate"	2.33	6	36	2015-12-19	"I Moderate"	3.83	7
37	2014-01-01	"I Moderate"	2.53	8	37	2016-02-08	"I Moderate"	2.9	5
38	2014-03-21	"I Moderate"	2.55	6	38	2016-06-01	"II Strong"	4.79	13
39	2014-04-26	"I Moderate"	2.5	5	39	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.83	29
40	2014-06-07	"I Moderate"	3.9	13	40	2018-05-11	"II Strong"	6.14	36
41	2014-07-21	"II Strong"	5.21	19	41	2018-06-25	"I Moderate"	3.76	26
42	2014-10-14	"I Moderate"	2.11	5	42	2018-07-26	"II Strong"	5.67	11
43	2014-11-01	"I Moderate"	3.23	12					
44	2015-01-10	"I Moderate"	3	10					
45	2015-11-11	"I Moderate"	1.95	7					
46	2015-11-28	"I Moderate"	3.08	16					
47	2015-12-18	"I Moderate"	3.24	8					
48	2016-04-11	"I Moderate"	2.49	7					
49	2016-06-02	"I Moderate"	3.93	16					
50	2016-09-13	"II Strong"	3.29	23					
51	2017-10-25	"I Moderate"	2.06	6					
52	2018-05-22	"II Strong"	7.21	23					
53	2018-07-01	"I Moderate"	2.82	8					
13. Great Belt					14. Western Baltic Sea				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-03-26	"I Moderate"	3.65	9	1	1990-02-04	"I Moderate"	2.34	5
2	1990-05-03	"I Moderate"	3.94	6	2	1990-03-25	"II Strong"	4.17	10
3	1994-07-10	"I Moderate"	3.43	6	3	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	4.58	10
4	1994-07-19	"II Strong"	5.8	26	4	1994-07-20	"I Moderate"	5.33	27

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5	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	3.48	10	5	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	3.78	13
6	1997-08-10	"II Strong"	5.53	32	6	1997-08-13	"II Strong"	5.31	30
7	1998-01-14	"I Moderate"	2.95	5	7	2000-05-13	"II Strong"	4.27	11
8	1999-09-09	"I Moderate"	2.16	5	8	2000-12-13	"I Moderate"	3.04	8
9	1999-09-24	"I Moderate"	2.64	8	9	2002-02-11	"I Moderate"	2.39	7
10	2000-05-10	"I Moderate"	3.81	14	10	2002-08-27	"II Strong"	4.14	30
11	2000-12-09	"I Moderate"	3.45	12	11	2003-08-05	"I Moderate"	3.9	9
12	2002-02-06	"I Moderate"	3.6	12	12	2005-11-12	"I Moderate"	2.47	6
13	2002-08-21	"II Strong"	3.68	32	13	2006-07-06	"I Moderate"	3.6	8
14	2003-08-06	"I Moderate"	4.24	9	14	2006-07-18	"I Moderate"	5.05	19
15	2005-01-09	"I Moderate"	2.79	8	15	2006-09-30	"I Moderate"	2.85	18
16	2005-11-04	"I Moderate"	2.51	13	16	2006-10-27	"I Moderate"	2.93	7
17	2006-07-06	"I Moderate"	3.87	5	17	2006-11-07	"I Moderate"	1.74	5
18	2006-07-18	"I Moderate"	4.2	19	18	2006-12-06	"I Moderate"	3.22	29
19	2006-09-25	"II Strong"	3.41	37	19	2007-01-09	"II Strong"	4.2	34
20	2006-11-24	"I Moderate"	1.89	6	20	2007-03-10	"I Moderate"	2.68	11
21	2006-12-06	"I Moderate"	3.55	20	21	2007-04-02	"I Moderate"	2.34	6
22	2006-12-31	"II Strong"	4.5	42	22	2007-04-11	"I Moderate"	2.53	8
23	2007-03-14	"I Moderate"	2.64	5	23	2007-04-24	"I Moderate"	3.55	5
24	2007-04-01	"I Moderate"	2.62	18	24	2008-01-29	"I Moderate"	2.53	6
25	2007-04-24	"I Moderate"	2.79	7	25	2008-02-25	"I Moderate"	2.82	10
26	2007-06-09	"II Strong"	4.65	5	26	2008-03-10	"I Moderate"	2.53	8
27	2008-01-27	"I Moderate"	2.9	8	27	2008-05-04	"III Severe"	6.3	10
28	2008-02-22	"I Moderate"	2.92	13	28	2010-07-09	"I Moderate"	4.51	9
29	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	5.47	12	29	2014-01-08	"I Moderate"	2.59	7
30	2009-07-01	"I Moderate"	3.77	5	30	2014-03-10	"I Moderate"	2.73	9
31	2010-07-09	"I Moderate"	3.87	9	31	2014-06-08	"I Moderate"	3.28	5
32	2014-03-15	"I Moderate"	3.18	14	32	2014-07-27	"I Moderate"	4.16	14
33	2014-06-08	"I Moderate"	3.76	9	33	2014-09-30	"II Strong"	3.27	31
34	2014-07-24	"I Moderate"	3.98	17	34	2014-11-06	"II Strong"	3.41	7
35	2014-10-01	"I Moderate"	3.16	29	35	2014-11-20	"II Strong"	3.13	12
36	2014-11-06	"II Strong"	3.55	7	36	2015-11-08	"II Strong"	2.98	16
37	2014-11-24	"I Moderate"	2.97	8	37	2015-12-08	"I Moderate"	2.51	8
38	2014-12-11	"I Moderate"	2.29	6	38	2015-12-21	"I Moderate"	3.48	15
39	2015-11-12	"I Moderate"	3.12	12	39	2016-06-21	"I Moderate"	3.29	12
40	2015-12-21	"I Moderate"	3.34	5	40	2016-09-06	"I Moderate"	3.55	30
41	2016-02-08	"I Moderate"	2.79	6	41	2017-04-01	"II Strong"	3.94	9
42	2016-05-30	"I Moderate"	4.14	14	42	2018-06-02	"II Strong"	4.13	20

43	2016-09-06	"II Strong"	3.96	31	43	2018-06-26	"I Moderate"	3.25	11
44	2017-04-02	"I Moderate"	2.73	12	44	2018-07-26	"I Moderate"	5.56	17
45	2018-05-12	"II Strong"	4.97	39	45	2018-09-03	"I Moderate"	2.5	5
46	2018-06-30	"I Moderate"	2.73	6					
47	2018-07-26	"I Moderate"	5.58	16					
15. Rügen East					16. Southern Baltic Sea				
No.	Start data	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Peak date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-02-21	"I Moderate"	2.98	8	1	1990-02-04	"I Moderate"	2.47	5
2	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	5.4	9	2	1990-03-27	"II Strong"	3.8	8
3	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	5.79	31	3	1990-05-03	"II Strong"	5.4	9
4	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	3.65	12	4	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	6.34	35
5	1997-08-10	"II Strong"	4.76	31	5	1995-08-17	"I Moderate"	3.61	10
6	1999-09-09	"I Moderate"	2.48	6	6	1995-10-28	"I Moderate"	2	8
7	2000-04-29	"II Strong"	4.3	7	7	1997-08-11	"II Strong"	5.13	32
8	2000-05-11	"I Moderate"	4.43	13	8	2000-05-15	"I Moderate"	4.28	9
9	2000-12-13	"I Moderate"	3.41	10	9	2002-08-26	"II Strong"	3.87	27
10	2002-02-12	"I Moderate"	2.99	8	10	2002-10-02	"I Moderate"	2.35	5
11	2002-08-27	"I Moderate"	3.53	24	11	2006-07-03	"II Strong"	5.54	33
12	2003-08-03	"I Moderate"	3.87	11	12	2006-09-25	"II Strong"	3.43	34
13	2005-01-10	"I Moderate"	3.53	8	13	2006-12-07	"II Strong"	3.2	64
14	2006-06-19	"I Moderate"	2.72	5	14	2007-04-12	"I Moderate"	2.45	7
15	2006-07-06	"I Moderate"	4.85	29	15	2007-06-08	"II Strong"	5.5	8
16	2006-09-23	"II Strong"	3.67	40	16	2008-02-21	"I Moderate"	2.52	26
17	2006-12-06	"II Strong"	3.95	15	17	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	5.26	7
18	2006-12-29	"I Moderate"	3.74	6	18	2010-07-09	"I Moderate"	4.63	9
19	2007-01-11	"II Strong"	5.06	17	19	2014-07-27	"I Moderate"	4.58	11
20	2007-02-01	"II Strong"	4	8	20	2014-10-14	"II Strong"	3.88	21
21	2007-03-29	"I Moderate"	3.56	10	21	2014-11-22	"II Strong"	2.87	19
22	2007-06-05	"II Strong"	5.82	10	22	2014-12-17	"I Moderate"	2.31	5
23	2008-02-25	"I Moderate"	3	17	23	2015-01-02	"I Moderate"	1.83	5
24	2008-05-06	"II Strong"	5.39	7	24	2015-01-13	"I Moderate"	2.03	6
25	2010-07-01	"I Moderate"	5.06	23	25	2015-03-08	"I Moderate"	1.89	5
26	2013-06-19	"I Moderate"	3.42	5	26	2015-11-05	"II Strong"	2.71	20
27	2014-01-09	"I Moderate"	3.25	5	27	2015-12-07	"I Moderate"	2.18	8
28	2014-06-09	"I Moderate"	4.15	5	28	2015-12-19	"I Moderate"	3.08	14
29	2014-07-30	"I Moderate"	4.2	5	29	2016-04-04	"I Moderate"	2.27	14
30	2014-09-18	"I Moderate"	2.34	6	30	2016-05-05	"I Moderate"	3.5	7
31	2014-10-16	"I Moderate"	3.41	5	31	2016-05-27	"I Moderate"	3.83	13

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32	2015-01-14	"I Moderate"	2.76	5	32	2016-06-23	"I Moderate"	4.2	11
33	2015-11-17	"I Moderate"	2.63	7	33	2016-09-07	"II Strong"	3.78	29
34	2015-12-09	"I Moderate"	3.38	5	34	2018-05-19	"II Strong"	4.58	34
35	2015-12-18	"I Moderate"	3.53	8	35	2018-07-26	"II Strong"	6.6	17
36	2016-05-30	"I Moderate"	4.08	11					
37	2016-09-06	"II Strong"	3.87	18					
38	2017-03-26	"I Moderate"	3.5	11					
39	2018-02-01	"I Moderate"	2.46	6					
40	2018-05-16	"I Moderate"	3.9	9					
41	2018-05-29	"I Moderate"	3.77	14					
42	2018-07-26	"I Moderate"	5.3	17					
43	2018-08-16	"I Moderate"	3.13	8					
44	2018-09-18	"I Moderate"	3.02	6					
45	2018-10-17	"I Moderate"	2.38	6					
46	2018-11-15	"I Moderate"	2.48	5					
17. Southeastern Baltic Sea					18. Central Baltic Sea				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1990-03-15	"I Moderate"	2.54	6	1	1990-03-30	"I Moderate"	2.63	6
2	1990-03-28	"II Strong"	3.37	8	2	1992-05-30	"II Strong"	6.13	10
3	1990-04-18	"I Moderate"	2.08	5	3	1993-05-20	"I Moderate"	3.68	5
4	1990-05-07	"I Moderate"	3.97	5	4	1994-07-12	"I Moderate"	5.66	5
5	1992-06-02	"I Moderate"	3.79	7	5	1994-07-26	"II Strong"	6.36	20
6	1993-05-20	"I Moderate"	4.14	5	6	1997-08-18	"II Strong"	4.79	25
7	1994-07-12	"I Moderate"	5.26	5	7	1999-09-10	"I Moderate"	2.6	6
8	1994-07-23	"II Strong"	7.35	23	8	1999-09-23	"I Moderate"	2.84	11
9	1997-08-11	"II Strong"	4.72	31	9	2000-12-09	"I Moderate"	2.77	19
10	2000-04-27	"II Strong"	4.26	5	10	2001-01-11	"I Moderate"	2.09	5
11	2000-12-08	"I Moderate"	2.57	15	11	2001-07-04	"I Moderate"	4.82	8
12	2001-01-07	"I Moderate"	2.07	5	12	2002-06-02	"II Strong"	5.51	12
13	2001-07-05	"I Moderate"	4.76	5	13	2002-08-14	"II Strong"	4.94	39
14	2002-08-20	"II Strong"	4.04	31	14	2003-07-18	"I Moderate"	4.97	19
15	2003-07-26	"I Moderate"	4.94	10	15	2005-07-06	"I Moderate"	4.74	10
16	2005-07-08	"I Moderate"	4.28	8	16	2006-07-02	"II Strong"	5.93	12
17	2005-10-07	"I Moderate"	2.53	10	17	2006-08-22	"I Moderate"	2.57	8
18	2006-07-02	"II Strong"	6.78	13	18	2006-09-24	"II Strong"	3.8	38
19	2006-09-24	"II Strong"	3.55	37	19	2007-01-09	"I Moderate"	2.51	21
20	2006-12-17	"I Moderate"	2.82	41	20	2007-06-07	"II Strong"	5.32	7
21	2007-02-02	"I Moderate"	2.42	7	21	2008-01-25	"I Moderate"	2.51	57

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22	2007-03-29	"I Moderate"	1.86	5	22	2008-05-03	"I Moderate"	3.95	9
23	2007-05-26	"I Moderate"	5.37	6	23	2008-06-05	"I Moderate"	4.21	5
24	2007-06-05	"II Strong"	6.17	12	24	2010-07-08	"I Moderate"	5.29	16
25	2008-02-18	"I Moderate"	2.21	26	25	2011-06-08	"I Moderate"	3.67	5
26	2008-05-04	"II Strong"	5.25	9	26	2013-09-11	"I Moderate"	2.37	7
27	2010-07-10	"I Moderate"	5.69	16	27	2014-05-21	"I Moderate"	4.44	6
28	2013-06-20	"I Moderate"	4.59	7	28	2014-07-25	"I Moderate"	4.98	19
29	2014-01-10	"I Moderate"	1.96	7	29	2014-11-21	"I Moderate"	2.17	10
30	2014-07-26	"I Moderate"	4.72	16	30	2014-12-07	"I Moderate"	2.07	6
31	2014-10-16	"I Moderate"	2.13	6	31	2014-12-19	"I Moderate"	1.75	5
32	2015-03-16	"I Moderate"	1.91	5	32	2015-03-01	"I Moderate"	2	20
33	2015-11-10	"I Moderate"	2.6	23	33	2015-10-04	"I Moderate"	2.6	5
34	2015-12-08	"I Moderate"	2.05	8	34	2015-10-17	"I Moderate"	2.73	14
35	2015-12-20	"I Moderate"	2.76	13	35	2015-11-05	"II Strong"	3.03	23
36	2016-02-01	"I Moderate"	1.92	6	36	2015-12-01	"I Moderate"	2.15	14
37	2016-02-17	"I Moderate"	2.23	14	37	2015-12-21	"I Moderate"	2.47	12
38	2016-03-13	"I Moderate"	1.97	18	38	2016-02-23	"I Moderate"	1.98	9
39	2016-04-04	"I Moderate"	2.19	14	39	2016-03-17	"I Moderate"	1.74	8
40	2016-05-02	"II Strong"	5.94	12	40	2016-04-05	"I Moderate"	2.08	11
41	2016-05-29	"II Strong"	6	11	41	2016-05-02	"III Severe"	7.42	10
42	2016-06-24	"I Moderate"	4.3	11	42	2016-06-01	"I Moderate"	3.9	5
43	2016-09-08	"I Moderate"	3.25	28	43	2016-09-14	"I Moderate"	2.98	16
44	2018-05-08	"II Strong"	5.7	10	44	2018-01-06	"I Moderate"	2.08	6
45	2018-05-26	"II Strong"	5.94	27	45	2018-05-08	"II Strong"	5.2	10
46	2018-07-20	"II Strong"	6.54	23	46	2018-05-23	"II Strong"	7.11	28
47	2018-09-03	"I Moderate"	3.02	5	47	2018-07-20	"II Strong"	6.4	22
48	2018-09-17	"II Strong"	3.62	5					
49	2018-11-14	"I Moderate"	2.41	8					
19. Northern Baltic Sea					20. Gulf of Riga				
No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration	No.	Start date	Category	I _{max}	Duration
1	1992-05-29	"II Strong"	6.88	11	1	1990-03-24	"II Strong"	3.15	8
2	1993-05-18	"I Moderate"	3.74	5	2	1990-04-21	"II Strong"	5.06	8
3	1994-07-27	"I Moderate"	5.52	16	3	1993-05-10	"I Moderate"	5.43	13
4	1996-08-19	"I Moderate"	3.05	12	4	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	7.18	6
5	1997-07-04	"I Moderate"	3.61	5	5	1994-07-26	"I Moderate"	6.24	17
6	1997-08-25	"II Strong"	5.21	18	6	1995-05-30	"I Moderate"	6.26	6
7	1999-06-14	"I Moderate"	3.45	7	7	1996-08-20	"I Moderate"	3.17	8
8	1999-09-23	"I Moderate"	2.95	11	8	1997-07-04	"I Moderate"	4.33	5

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9	2000-10-24	"I Moderate"	2.55	10	9	1997-08-26	"I Moderate"	3.38	10
10	2000-12-08	"I Moderate"	3.24	14	10	1999-06-17	"I Moderate"	5.53	7
11	2001-07-05	"I Moderate"	4.48	7	11	1999-09-07	"I Moderate"	2.66	6
12	2002-06-03	"II Strong"	5.99	12	12	2001-07-05	"I Moderate"	5.57	7
13	2002-08-11	"II Strong"	5.09	39	13	2002-06-08	"I Moderate"	4.57	6
14	2003-07-20	"I Moderate"	5.61	17	14	2002-08-22	"II Strong"	4.08	29
15	2005-07-05	"I Moderate"	5.8	11	15	2003-07-28	"I Moderate"	5.2	9
16	2006-07-05	"I Moderate"	5.09	7	16	2005-07-07	"I Moderate"	4.58	12
17	2006-08-25	"I Moderate"	2.86	9	17	2005-10-08	"I Moderate"	2.2	16
18	2006-09-26	"I Moderate"	3.61	31	18	2006-07-05	"I Moderate"	5.85	10
19	2007-01-09	"I Moderate"	2.76	12	19	2006-09-27	"I Moderate"	3.37	19
20	2007-01-27	"I Moderate"	2.2	9	20	2006-12-03	"I Moderate"	3.4	23
21	2007-06-06	"I Moderate"	4.88	8	21	2007-01-01	"II Strong"	4.16	36
22	2008-01-25	"I Moderate"	2.44	12	22	2007-03-29	"I Moderate"	1.93	5
23	2008-02-11	"I Moderate"	2.57	41	23	2007-06-06	"I Moderate"	5.83	9
24	2010-07-04	"I Moderate"	5.09	20	24	2008-01-30	"I Moderate"	1.92	7
25	2011-11-09	"I Moderate"	2.31	6	25	2008-02-25	"I Moderate"	1.71	5
26	2011-12-24	"I Moderate"	2.48	5	26	2008-03-04	"II Strong"	2.44	18
27	2013-09-10	"I Moderate"	3.08	14	27	2008-04-26	"I Moderate"	3.81	5
28	2014-05-22	"I Moderate"	4.01	5	28	2010-07-11	"I Moderate"	5.81	14
29	2014-07-23	"I Moderate"	5.92	22	29	2010-08-13	"I Moderate"	3.91	5
30	2014-09-16	"I Moderate"	2.56	7	30	2011-06-08	"I Moderate"	6.25	5
31	2014-12-07	"I Moderate"	2.23	5	31	2011-07-07	"I Moderate"	4.59	5
32	2015-02-12	"I Moderate"	1.84	5	32	2011-12-03	"I Moderate"	2.57	6
33	2015-02-22	"I Moderate"	2.13	26	33	2011-12-25	"I Moderate"	2.68	5
34	2015-09-26	"I Moderate"	2.43	8	34	2012-01-16	"I Moderate"	2.41	6
35	2015-10-14	"II Strong"	3.55	44	35	2013-05-17	"I Moderate"	4.94	5
36	2015-12-07	"I Moderate"	2.44	9	36	2013-06-02	"I Moderate"	5.48	11
37	2015-12-21	"I Moderate"	2.71	12	37	2013-06-23	"I Moderate"	5.01	6
38	2016-04-04	"I Moderate"	2.23	14	38	2013-09-11	"I Moderate"	2.61	6
39	2016-05-02	"III Severe"	6.58	14	39	2014-05-20	"I Moderate"	5.46	7
40	2016-09-20	"I Moderate"	2.74	10	40	2014-07-24	"I Moderate"	4.82	22
41	2018-05-12	"II Strong"	5.77	6	41	2014-09-16	"I Moderate"	2.34	6
42	2018-05-21	"II Strong"	6.24	15	42	2015-03-07	"I Moderate"	1.77	18
43	2018-07-15	"I Moderate"	6.17	27	43	2015-09-24	"I Moderate"	2.31	7
					44	2015-10-28	"I Moderate"	1.98	6
					45	2015-11-10	"II Strong"	3.51	23
					46	2015-12-07	"I Moderate"	3.48	10

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					47	2015-12-21	"II Strong"	4.22	11
					48	2016-02-12	"II Strong"	2.34	6
					49	2016-02-24	"I Moderate"	1.44	8
					50	2016-03-15	"I Moderate"	1.58	5
					51	2016-05-06	"II Strong"	8.12	7
					52	1990-03-24	"I Moderate"	6.77	7
					53	1990-04-21	"I Moderate"	4.44	5
					54	1993-05-10	"I Moderate"	2.74	14
					55	1994-07-12	"II Strong"	7.2	24
					56	1994-07-26	"I Moderate"	5.76	22
					57	1995-05-30	"I Moderate"	4.23	8

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

1. Engl. Channel West					2. Engl. Channel East				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-04-24	7	1.45	9	1	1998-04-25	66	4.24	168.7
2	1998-05-08	7	1.61	9.6	2	1999-04-13	56	9.04	177.2
3	1998-05-25	14	1.86	18.9	3	1999-06-15	10	3.17	23.4
4	1999-04-07	51	1.91	61.2	4	2000-04-06	8	5	32.8
5	2001-04-24	31	2.91	47.2	5	2000-05-19	26	3.75	67.5
6	2002-05-11	24	1.78	33.6	6	2000-08-02	8	3.45	20.7
7	2003-04-06	16	3.22	29.9	7	2001-05-05	39	11.85	202.8
8	2003-04-28	20	2.78	35.8	8	2001-06-25	11	3.33	28.2
9	2004-04-06	6	1.58	8.3	9	2001-07-25	36	4.63	90.1
10	2004-04-18	7	1.82	9.6	10	2002-05-14	23	4.7	67.4
11	2005-04-19	41	2.68	60.8	11	2002-06-13	21	5.18	57.2
12	2006-03-29	6	1.35	7.7	12	2002-07-12	9	5.34	28.7
13	2006-04-26	9	1.84	13.6	13	2002-08-14	6	3.24	15.5
14	2007-04-02	6	1.44	7.9	14	2003-03-17	103	8.65	457.9
15	2007-04-14	51	3.02	80.3	15	2003-07-08	11	3.82	36.2
16	2008-04-04	11	2.01	17.5	16	2003-08-04	10	4.09	29.2
17	2008-04-27	17	2.01	25.7	17	2004-04-07	31	4.11	90.6
18	2008-05-21	27	1.87	36.5	18	2004-05-16	84	5.13	251.3
19	2009-03-25	7	1.66	10.2	19	2005-02-16	17	3.07	44.6
20	2009-04-09	35	1.73	46.7	20	2005-04-07	7	3.01	18.7
21	2010-03-29	8	2.09	14.6	21	2005-04-22	70	7.76	241.8
22	2010-04-12	38	1.89	58.1	22	2005-07-09	7	3.39	15.5
23	2011-04-19	39	2.45	59.4	23	2005-08-10	7	2.9	14.7
24	2012-04-23	12	1.39	15	24	2006-03-02	50	5.37	169.3
25	2013-04-06	26	1.65	31.7	25	2006-04-30	6	2.76	15.2
26	2013-05-22	36	3.08	52.3	26	2006-05-14	16	3.41	43.7
27	2014-04-13	9	2.23	16.1	27	2006-06-06	45	5.15	101.7
28	2014-05-13	7	1.71	10.3	28	2007-03-19	7	3.11	19.1
29	2015-03-22	18	2.05	25.6	29	2007-04-02	38	10.83	196.5
30	2015-04-17	9	1.92	14.4	30	2007-05-16	15	4.63	51.9
31	2016-03-19	14	2.1	20.8	31	2007-07-01	8	2.78	18.6
32	2016-05-07	8	1.93	12.7	32	2007-08-02	10	2.66	23.7
33	2017-03-29	6	1.51	7.5	33	2008-03-10	7	3.13	19.5

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

34	2017-04-23	8	1.37	9.5	34	2008-04-05	83	6.59	286.4
35	2017-05-10	10	1.32	11.1	35	2009-03-02	34	3.56	84.4
36	2018-04-15	38	1.79	43.2	36	2009-04-23	72	9.17	231.8
					37	2010-03-04	98	8.8	314.6
					38	2011-03-18	9	5.27	29.9
					39	2011-04-06	62	10.05	254.9
					40	2011-06-20	8	3.89	20.7
					41	2012-03-14	54	6.57	160.7
					42	2012-05-12	8	5.44	22
					43	2012-08-13	6	3.43	17.2
					44	2013-04-06	41	6.66	130.6
					45	2013-05-28	22	4.2	60.7
					46	2014-02-18	15	2.97	38.1
					47	2014-03-17	10	4.71	35.2
					48	2014-04-08	15	6	70.3
					49	2014-05-03	22	5.95	84.7
					50	2015-02-19	19	3.35	50
					51	2015-03-22	68	8.08	288.8
					52	2016-03-24	8	2.53	18.6
					53	2016-04-10	50	5.66	174.2
					54	2016-08-18	10	3.05	23.2
					55	2017-03-01	11	2.79	24
					56	2017-03-28	81	5	213.6
					57	2018-02-12	17	2.62	37.8
					58	2018-04-17	40	7.83	127.8
					59	2018-06-23	9	2.46	19.2
3. Southwestern North Sea					4. Dogger				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-04-27	29	9.48	118.4	1	1998-02-22	17	2.48	25.4
2	1999-04-13	53	11.53	274	2	1998-04-20	26	2.15	36.8
3	1999-07-11	7	2.98	15.3	3	1999-02-24	6	1.22	6.4
4	2000-02-14	12	3.42	38.7	4	1999-03-12	62	1.45	64.3
5	2000-04-07	19	3.36	51.8	5	1999-05-19	9	0.85	7.1
6	2000-05-05	7	4.01	20.2	6	2000-02-14	18	1.75	22.1
7	2001-04-01	58	15.32	313.3	7	2000-03-16	44	1.5	48.3
8	2001-06-10	6	3.12	15.3	8	2001-02-12	12	1.42	12
9	2002-02-13	26	3.61	82	9	2001-03-02	21	1.96	28.6
10	2002-03-24	24	5.16	78	10	2001-04-04	35	1.76	43.1

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

11	2002-05-02	7	2.78	16.1	11	2002-02-11	9	1.39	8.9
12	2002-05-16	17	4.57	45.1	12	2002-03-02	77	2.02	90.9
13	2003-02-15	19	4.28	61	13	2002-05-25	12	0.89	9.1
14	2003-03-15	70	12.68	390.1	14	2003-02-12	97	2.49	121
15	2004-02-22	8	5.72	31.9	15	2004-02-19	86	3.03	119
16	2004-03-10	20	5.01	71.6	16	2005-02-16	24	1.76	29.6
17	2004-04-06	63	6.33	236.2	17	2005-03-22	61	2.02	68.4
18	2005-02-12	13	5.9	60.2	18	2006-02-13	9	1.67	13.1
19	2005-03-09	7	5.86	28.2	19	2006-03-01	10	2	18.1
20	2005-04-07	64	6.02	241.7	20	2006-03-20	53	2.13	74
21	2006-02-22	24	6.04	89.1	21	2006-05-24	11	1.3	9.3
22	2006-03-24	42	4.61	150.8	22	2007-03-03	46	2.93	71.2
23	2006-05-18	15	4.14	48.7	23	2008-02-08	92	3.64	149.2
24	2007-02-12	7	3.24	20	24	2009-02-08	9	1.76	12.9
25	2007-03-02	9	3.23	26.2	25	2009-02-27	82	1.96	103
26	2007-03-19	49	13.4	284.3	26	2010-02-08	7	1.4	8.5
27	2007-05-15	9	5.06	36.1	27	2010-02-27	11	1.53	15.4
28	2008-02-25	21	4.56	80.7	28	2010-03-19	60	3	98.3
29	2008-03-29	60	10.52	326.5	29	2011-03-06	59	2.15	81.6
30	2009-03-03	93	7.9	354.1	30	2012-02-20	58	2.67	89.3
31	2010-03-01	94	10.59	413.2	31	2012-05-03	17	1.2	17.1
32	2010-06-17	12	3.94	36	32	2013-02-28	18	1.99	27.5
33	2011-03-08	78	10.51	334.4	33	2013-03-28	39	3.01	65
34	2012-03-09	54	5.14	176.4	34	2013-05-28	9	0.93	7.5
35	2012-05-30	8	3.17	23.3	35	2014-02-14	44	2.19	63.1
36	2013-03-09	9	6.33	40.5	36	2014-04-07	39	2.38	46.4
37	2013-03-27	53	8.21	231.2	37	2015-02-18	27	1.92	41.3
38	2013-05-28	13	7.54	79.9	38	2015-03-29	38	2.94	54.4
39	2014-02-16	42	5.85	126.3	39	2015-05-13	8	1.46	9
40	2014-04-10	15	6.93	67.7	40	2015-05-31	9	1.16	9.5
41	2014-05-03	22	8.05	102.5	41	2016-02-15	16	1.58	18
42	2015-02-10	97	17.8	392.1	42	2016-03-14	67	3.19	86.1
43	2016-02-16	7	3.32	21.2	43	2017-02-27	73	1.8	87.6
44	2016-03-01	32	3.73	94	44	2018-02-14	13	1.68	15.7
45	2016-04-08	41	7.43	185.7	45	2018-03-22	9	1.88	12.3
46	2016-06-07	7	3.27	18.1	46	2018-04-16	27	1.9	35.4
47	2017-02-27	79	6.91	288.2					
48	2018-02-13	14	3.61	41.5					

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

49	2018-03-17	7	4.39	26.6					
50	2018-04-16	36	6.42	159.7					
51	2018-06-18	8	4.67	25.2					
5. Forties					6. Viking				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-02-28	12	1.27	11	1	1998-04-30	35	3.24	50.5
2	1998-04-24	24	2.68	39	2	1999-04-16	52	2.54	56.5
3	1999-04-03	61	1.66	65.7	3	2000-05-04	18	1.73	20.1
4	2000-02-17	11	1.04	8.9	4	2001-03-22	6	1.04	5.1
5	2000-03-20	6	0.72	4.1	5	2001-04-22	39	3.08	43.1
6	2000-04-04	42	2.74	41.4	6	2002-04-08	18	1.1	15.2
7	2001-04-06	68	4.05	80.9	7	2002-05-02	37	4.11	53.9
8	2002-02-27	16	0.87	12.3	8	2002-06-21	12	1.18	11.1
9	2002-03-30	70	4.15	88.9	9	2003-03-28	74	2.4	80.7
10	2003-03-22	68	2.43	93	10	2004-03-26	19	1.01	15
11	2003-06-20	6	0.94	5.3	11	2004-04-26	55	2.69	68
12	2004-02-25	7	1	5.9	12	2005-04-18	53	2.31	62.3
13	2004-03-29	62	3.67	72.6	13	2006-02-27	13	3.14	19.2
14	2005-03-28	68	3.25	77	14	2006-04-20	25	1.85	28.6
15	2006-04-05	38	2.61	50.6	15	2006-05-27	11	0.99	8.6
16	2007-03-17	75	6.33	117.3	16	2006-06-23	13	1.22	9.8
17	2008-02-27	34	1.13	27.5	17	2007-03-29	62	3.09	80.1
18	2008-04-16	38	5.83	67.4	18	2008-03-27	74	4.18	114.4
19	2008-05-31	6	0.79	4.3	19	2009-04-16	70	1.96	84.4
20	2008-06-17	9	0.81	6.2	20	2010-03-16	11	1.42	13.1
21	2009-03-19	80	2.23	100.9	21	2010-04-12	52	3.66	71.2
22	2010-03-14	84	4.07	120.4	22	2010-06-08	16	1.26	14.4
23	2011-03-23	10	1.93	13.1	23	2011-04-03	29	3.68	48.4
24	2011-04-14	17	1.88	19.1	24	2011-05-13	8	1.55	10
25	2011-05-21	16	2.05	19.5	25	2011-05-29	20	1.77	27.6
26	2012-03-20	32	3.23	47	26	2012-03-23	15	3.18	28.1
27	2012-04-27	32	3.07	52.3	27	2012-04-14	50	1.63	43.5
28	2013-03-10	8	0.72	5.2	28	2013-03-14	34	2.54	41
29	2013-03-25	71	5.05	81.4	29	2013-05-09	26	2.08	30.4
30	2014-03-16	15	1.3	13.9	30	2014-04-02	31	2.11	35.1
31	2014-04-10	51	4.44	77.5	31	2014-05-11	19	2.17	24.8
32	2014-06-08	6	1.01	5.3	32	2015-04-06	65	2.45	77
33	2015-04-01	72	5.32	104	33	2016-03-28	35	1.88	39.5

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

34	2016-03-27	75	2.12	81.4	34	2016-05-14	28	1.21	26.7
35	2017-02-28	6	0.72	4.3	35	2017-04-13	44	1.74	38.2
36	2017-03-17	56	1.77	58.7	36	2018-03-28	14	1.11	11.8
37	2017-05-18	6	0.81	4.2	37	2018-04-17	41	3.06	39.6
38	2017-06-28	8	0.96	5					
39	2018-03-17	14	0.82	10.5					
40	2018-04-06	42	2.08	40.4					
8. German Bight					9. Fisher				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-03-05	9	2.97	24.7	1	1998-03-02	16	2.27	25.2
2	1998-04-30	19	5.17	57.2	2	1998-05-02	33	8.26	53.1
3	1999-03-25	8	4	25.5	3	1999-02-21	8	2.01	14.4
4	1999-04-12	30	5.35	92	4	1999-03-20	14	2.42	20.6
5	1999-05-26	7	2.55	14.3	5	1999-04-13	44	1.81	53.4
6	2000-04-05	57	7.78	209.8	6	2000-03-22	9	1.32	10.9
7	2001-03-10	7	2.55	15.7	7	2000-04-07	7	1.83	11.3
8	2001-03-31	24	6.17	98	8	2000-04-27	19	6.06	43.9
9	2001-04-30	14	3.05	30.2	9	2000-05-30	7	1.52	9.6
10	2001-06-02	20	2.93	50.5	10	2001-03-16	39	2.08	55.6
11	2002-03-24	20	3.71	58.9	11	2001-05-02	8	1.33	8.8
12	2002-05-14	21	8.33	72.2	12	2001-06-05	21	1.91	26.5
13	2003-03-20	51	7.41	198.5	13	2002-02-26	49	3.57	70.7
14	2003-05-17	34	4.86	103.3	14	2002-04-22	46	3.06	58.9
15	2004-03-20	80	10.43	319.4	15	2003-02-20	11	1.89	15.2
16	2005-03-07	14	4.07	43.1	16	2003-03-13	85	4.18	142.3
17	2005-04-09	61	9.88	239.6	17	2004-02-16	86	3.46	143.4
18	2006-04-04	42	7.23	167.3	18	2004-05-20	20	2.48	32.9
19	2006-05-26	17	6.01	60.3	19	2005-03-04	19	2.18	34.6
20	2007-03-21	9	4.09	30.8	20	2005-03-31	32	2.66	55.8
21	2007-04-06	68	12.08	349.5	21	2005-05-11	6	1.81	9.1
22	2008-03-20	12	5.02	45.1	22	2005-05-23	10	1.57	12.3
23	2008-04-08	50	9.5	264.4	23	2006-03-14	63	2.83	92.2
24	2009-03-21	79	9.97	322.8	24	2006-05-23	27	2.85	38.6
25	2010-03-23	45	7.05	160.1	25	2007-03-12	49	3.36	95.8
26	2010-05-17	13	5.27	33.2	26	2007-05-18	18	2.96	28.4
27	2011-03-07	9	4.06	28.9	27	2008-02-28	30	2.61	55.1
28	2011-03-25	62	10.58	254	28	2008-04-11	67	6.62	149.1
29	2012-03-10	13	3.72	38.7	29	2009-02-23	16	4.18	29.8

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

30	2012-03-30	40	4.43	136	30	2009-03-18	80	8.9	163.1
31	2012-05-26	7	3	17.5	31	2010-03-13	21	2.79	43
32	2013-05-25	26	6.23	86.7	32	2010-04-10	40	1.68	49.2
33	2014-03-07	23	4.41	69.1	33	2010-05-28	20	2.04	29.4
34	2014-04-10	22	8.01	79.5	34	2011-03-06	42	4.17	98.3
35	2015-03-06	7	5.18	29.2	35	2011-04-25	8	2.14	10.5
36	2015-04-01	29	5.12	96.3	36	2011-06-02	25	2.75	30.5
37	2015-05-21	6	3.48	18.1	37	2012-02-16	55	10.95	167.1
38	2016-03-13	12	3.97	33	38	2012-04-28	12	1.7	15.2
39	2016-04-13	32	3.95	89.8	39	2012-05-20	14	2.17	17.9
40	2017-03-16	8	3.56	23.6	40	2013-03-01	16	3.08	29.6
41	2017-04-10	34	6.02	102.7	41	2013-03-23	45	3.69	79.8
42	2017-05-29	6	3.7	19.3	42	2013-06-03	8	1.24	8.6
43	2018-04-21	47	5.13	145.2	43	2014-03-08	22	2.03	35.7
10. Utsire					11. Skagerrak				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-05-02	25	3.7	54.2	1	1998-03-05	25	2.46	51.9
2	1999-03-24	16	2.71	34.9	2	1999-02-21	13	3.48	34.3
3	1999-04-28	24	1.77	34.7	3	2000-04-07	10	2.21	18.8
4	2000-05-06	19	1.94	29.9	4	2001-03-18	16	5.14	54.9
5	2001-03-13	14	3.8	34.6	5	2001-04-10	14	2.25	25.3
6	2001-04-15	27	1.92	37.5	6	2002-03-15	12	3.96	36.9
7	2002-05-01	10	2.5	18.4	7	2003-02-16	9	2.7	25.3
8	2003-03-11	8	5.13	35.3	8	2003-03-10	31	6.66	117.4
9	2003-03-30	20	2.66	35.3	9	2003-04-17	11	3.54	27.7
10	2004-03-01	24	3.41	44.8	10	2004-02-17	57	6.41	196.5
11	2004-04-10	6	1.52	8.4	11	2005-02-22	44	11.03	164.8
12	2004-04-24	7	1.79	11.2	12	2005-04-17	12	3.1	30.2
13	2005-02-17	23	7.93	60.8	13	2006-02-21	6	8.45	42.9
14	2005-04-16	13	2.96	24.4	14	2006-03-05	22	7.08	85.6
15	2005-05-05	11	1.65	15.7	15	2006-04-03	20	4.02	58.6
16	2006-02-18	23	3.51	50.1	16	2007-03-15	40	9.31	202.2
17	2006-04-11	32	2.04	49.6	17	2008-02-12	7	4.84	28.5
18	2007-03-22	17	6.91	53.6	18	2008-02-26	39	7.44	172.1
19	2007-04-16	21	2.67	34.5	19	2009-02-10	7	9.61	47.2
20	2008-03-16	16	3.89	41.3	20	2009-03-31	62	8.01	244.3
21	2008-04-17	42	4.93	96.4	21	2010-02-28	60	5.19	170.3
22	2009-02-09	9	2.34	19.3	22	2011-02-10	9	7.35	68.2

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

23	2009-02-24	20	6.95	57.4	23	2011-03-06	37	9.84	201.4
24	2009-04-17	32	2.36	56.5	24	2012-02-14	55	27.97	373.1
25	2010-02-09	9	3.46	25.6	25	2013-02-22	71	26.45	394.3
26	2010-02-26	21	2.23	35.7	26	2014-03-09	87	7.87	328.6
27	2010-04-06	13	1.63	20.1	27	2015-03-03	75	8.32	276.5
28	2010-05-08	6	1.71	9.5	28	2016-02-20	13	7.8	57.4
29	2011-03-21	30	6.72	86.9	29	2016-03-14	56	4.95	163.7
30	2011-05-03	12	2.05	19.6	30	2017-03-14	15	3.8	44.2
31	2012-02-22	9	3.94	32	31	2017-04-08	21	4.05	54.3
32	2012-03-20	33	4.75	69.7	32	2018-03-13	25	13.18	137.2
33	2012-04-29	9	1.94	13.4	33	2018-04-22	52	3.58	122.9
34	2013-02-22	56	10.36	172.3					
35	2014-03-09	58	5.1	130.5					
36	2014-05-14	19	2.07	29.5					
37	2015-03-11	14	2.54	27.3					
38	2015-04-03	44	6.34	107.3					
39	2016-02-22	39	3.16	74.8					
40	2016-04-10	19	2.13	31					
41	2017-03-24	42	3.25	76.5					
42	2018-02-25	10	1.85	16.6					
43	2018-03-14	24	6.37	63.5					
44	2018-04-17	17	2.04	27.8					
12. Kattegat					13. Great Belt				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-04-17	6	2.45	12.9	1	1998-03-07	7	5.32	32
2	1999-04-01	7	3.12	20.5	2	2003-02-13	17	18.28	198.3
3	1999-04-20	17	3.24	47.5	3	2003-03-10	30	10.83	214.5
4	2000-02-14	22	4.22	67	4	2003-04-17	8	10.07	57.7
5	2001-03-18	13	6.35	56.1	5	2004-02-15	24	16.24	274.3
6	2001-04-18	16	3.47	42.7	6	2005-03-17	42	17.11	362.7
7	2002-02-25	16	5.08	65.8	7	2006-02-04	9	21.37	99.3
8	2003-02-13	17	20.95	158.8	8	2006-02-24	14	19.78	194.7
9	2003-03-10	46	7.41	176.8	9	2007-03-12	71	35.08	1243.5
10	2004-02-14	62	24.23	413.9	10	2008-02-07	8	16	95.5
11	2005-02-23	98	15.49	479	11	2008-03-19	9	13.7	110.8
12	2006-02-04	6	15.51	87.9	12	2009-03-15	28	25.95	359.1
13	2006-02-24	31	20.96	309.1	13	2009-04-18	10	12.04	110.7
14	2006-04-02	66	14.08	397.7	14	2010-03-01	6	16.49	82.4

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

15	2007-03-10	58	22.25	498.5	15	2011-03-05	67	39.4	1586.3
16	2008-02-26	43	11.7	329.9	16	2012-02-06	26	11.15	213.1
17	2009-02-21	9	25.46	152.2	17	2012-03-11	12	16.81	149.3
18	2009-03-14	64	7.81	322	18	2013-03-02	13	10.48	107.2
19	2010-03-01	21	6.75	107.9	19	2013-03-28	9	12.21	72
20	2010-04-06	22	6.74	120.5	20	2014-03-10	8	11.12	84.2
21	2011-03-05	67	42.93	979.7	21	2014-04-22	9	13.14	97.2
22	2012-02-12	66	42.3	505.9	22	2015-03-07	7	39.42	235.4
23	2012-05-03	7	4.26	26	23	2015-04-03	6	27.53	141.3
24	2013-02-25	58	13.58	379.2	24	2015-04-15	17	35.26	437.7
25	2014-03-09	26	15.86	198.7	25	2017-03-24	8	32.4	149.6
26	2014-04-11	27	12.78	184.8	26	2018-03-17	7	10.98	71.1
27	2015-03-02	16	31.05	243.3					
28	2015-03-30	57	21.05	628.7					
29	2016-02-20	11	12.55	84.3					
30	2016-03-17	62	5.5	240					
31	2017-03-14	61	19.76	451.4					
32	2018-02-22	9	16.7	79					
33	2018-03-17	6	11.89	63.6					
34	2018-03-30	9	7.51	47.7					
14. Western Baltic Sea					15. Rügen East				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	2000-04-06	7	3.38	21.3	1	2000-04-08	6	8.32	40.6
2	2001-03-16	15	4.16	48	2	2000-04-24	29	10.18	208.1
3	2003-02-06	11	9.72	78.4	3	2001-03-18	13	10.36	96.3
4	2003-02-23	7	18.01	67.6	4	2003-03-13	12	28.5	254.2
5	2003-03-12	13	10.38	97.3	5	2003-03-31	12	17.89	142.5
6	2003-03-31	9	6.92	50.9	6	2003-04-19	7	19.47	113.1
7	2005-03-13	67	12.46	434.1	7	2004-03-17	38	27.05	455.5
8	2007-03-08	78	29.2	848.6	8	2004-05-01	13	20.81	150.2
9	2008-02-28	31	11.35	264.4	9	2005-03-21	43	26.08	703.3
10	2009-03-14	13	11.66	123.1	10	2006-03-20	15	15.34	198.8
11	2010-03-01	20	12.23	196.6	11	2009-04-03	23	21.49	392.7
12	2010-03-31	7	8.96	55.1	12	2010-04-16	14	18.82	194.9
13	2011-02-23	62	29.39	1020.4	13	2011-03-21	8	26.03	189.4
14	2012-02-14	56	15.5	445.3	14	2011-04-20	24	23.17	409
15	2013-04-02	8	9.47	68.5	15	2012-02-28	41	17.19	497.2
16	2014-02-09	19	11.97	132	16	2013-04-02	10	36.05	280.5

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

17	2014-03-07	20	30.32	272.3	17	2014-02-16	11	12.86	129
18	2015-02-22	22	32.12	333.6	18	2014-03-06	13	56.42	398.2
19	2015-04-01	8	16.11	91.7	19	2014-04-27	6	13.64	67.4
20	2015-04-15	39	18.26	380.3	20	2015-02-25	17	24.01	255.8
21	2017-03-12	20	21.37	248.8	21	2015-04-16	7	13.86	73.8
22	2017-04-08	55	12.28	410	22	2016-03-10	9	16.26	74.1
23	2018-03-17	7	15.21	82.5	23	2017-03-19	13	20.65	205
24	2018-04-01	9	11.44	71.6	24	2018-04-16	9	15.47	105.4
25	2018-04-16	8	8.57	54.1					
16. Southern Baltic Sea					17. Southeastern Baltic Sea				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	2000-04-03	10	5.03	35.7	1	1998-04-25	16	6.37	64.8
2	2001-03-21	13	3.88	43.1	2	1999-04-29	6	3.83	24.3
3	2003-02-23	47	15.5	253.2	3	2000-04-19	38	5.99	148.3
4	2003-04-19	7	4.48	27.2	4	2001-04-29	15	3.65	41.7
5	2004-03-22	27	8.22	111.1	5	2002-04-30	12	12.42	83.6
6	2005-03-22	36	7.94	173.6	6	2004-03-31	34	10.15	212
7	2006-04-03	18	6.46	77.7	7	2005-04-04	40	15.14	257.7
8	2007-04-02	29	9.58	146.1	8	2006-04-13	14	10.1	82
9	2009-03-19	45	10.47	268.8	9	2006-05-07	10	7.58	56.4
10	2010-03-25	34	8.99	185.3	10	2007-03-23	46	12.97	303.5
11	2011-03-07	6	6.77	35.8	11	2008-03-22	80	24.87	1051
12	2011-03-21	10	9.29	72.3	12	2009-04-03	40	11.4	270.8
13	2011-04-08	26	11.37	190	13	2010-04-05	30	14.32	198.9
14	2012-02-15	63	8.48	330.2	14	2011-03-23	55	16.72	481.8
15	2013-03-03	18	6.13	87.1	15	2012-05-03	10	6.96	42.9
16	2013-04-02	24	7.78	136.3	16	2013-04-04	33	7.74	180.8
17	2014-03-08	13	15.18	94.7	17	2014-04-25	6	6.06	29.4
18	2015-03-06	17	6.63	89.5	18	2015-04-21	8	8.34	50.1
19	2015-04-14	15	7.41	79.4	19	2016-04-17	6	5.94	26.8
20	2016-03-17	7	7.78	44.8	20	2016-05-04	11	8.79	76.8
21	2017-03-13	36	6.87	189.5	21	2017-04-21	13	9.43	72.2
22	2018-03-17	6	6.05	34.9	22	2018-05-06	8	12.38	72.2
23	2018-03-29	9	4.82	42.4					
18. Central Baltic Sea					19. Northern Baltic Sea				
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum	No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum
1	1998-04-30	8	4.5	27	1	1998-04-25	26	5.3	94.1
2	2002-05-06	6	6.1	29.1	2	1999-05-21	7	4.81	26.4

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

3	2002-05-19	7	5.81	37.6	3	2002-04-05	13	5.17	63.2
4	2003-03-26	12	8.73	76.2	4	2002-04-29	26	8.96	166.7
5	2003-04-15	27	10.27	187.2	5	2003-03-14	48	15.69	334.6
6	2004-04-01	45	8.75	233.1	6	2003-05-23	13	6.69	64.1
7	2005-04-02	26	10.97	154.2	7	2004-03-28	58	11.31	371.7
8	2005-05-16	7	5.52	33.7	8	2005-03-19	6	9.6	41.9
9	2006-04-05	21	8.27	117.5	9	2005-04-02	51	11.32	357.3
10	2006-05-09	15	5.82	65.5	10	2006-04-14	38	17.86	271.1
11	2007-04-02	29	13	209.1	11	2007-03-29	40	11.28	273.6
12	2008-04-13	66	21.41	767.1	12	2007-05-18	7	6.98	38.2
13	2009-04-08	31	11.24	230.5	13	2008-04-14	32	14.86	326.6
14	2010-03-30	36	13.65	302.6	14	2008-05-24	70	11.02	531.4
15	2011-03-21	66	12.81	456.2	15	2009-03-24	49	12.26	379.3
16	2012-04-03	8	7.15	50.2	16	2010-03-06	14	19.47	105.4
17	2012-05-01	11	7.24	59.5	17	2010-04-03	39	18.28	326
18	2013-04-03	34	15.39	266.1	18	2011-03-07	6	7.2	35
19	2014-03-14	52	16.59	343.6	19	2011-04-11	32	12.04	246.7
20	2015-04-14	13	22.86	118.9	20	2011-05-20	7	6.75	38.1
21	2016-03-19	11	10.55	67.7	21	2012-03-04	23	10.39	154.3
22	2016-04-11	12	13.28	87.7	22	2012-04-19	23	12.68	164.6
23	2016-05-05	11	8.08	68.1	23	2013-03-08	10	9.66	73.3
24	2017-03-17	16	8.04	98.7	24	2013-03-27	41	21.06	367.6
25	2018-03-19	10	8.4	53.7	25	2014-03-21	48	25.57	383.8
26	2018-04-16	35	29.62	312.4	26	2015-03-06	18	12.24	135.7
					27	2015-04-13	16	11.41	156.7
					28	2016-03-18	7	13.97	59.8
					29	2016-04-12	13	18.49	124.3
					30	2016-05-05	12	9.93	91.7
					31	2017-03-17	54	15.57	462.4
					32	2018-03-27	9	12.53	76.5
					33	2018-04-17	28	36.41	365.7
20. Gulf of Riga									
No	Start	Length	Peak Value	Sum					
1	1999-06-14	7	7.59	45.5					
2	2000-05-26	12	8.62	96					
3	2000-06-16	12	13.14	124.1					
4	2001-03-26	6	8.6	44.3					
5	2001-04-26	9	8.63	71.3					

Appendix II: Spring bloom events

6	2001-05-28	6	9.11	44					
7	2002-04-30	41	31.92	837.3					
8	2002-06-18	30	21.59	445					
9	2003-03-24	14	23.94	230.6					
10	2003-04-16	28	32.04	665.8					
11	2003-05-21	22	19.26	328.8					
12	2004-04-02	54	32.14	1128.7					
13	2004-06-01	7	19.43	120.7					
14	2004-06-22	6	17.18	79.7					
15	2005-04-17	43	32.03	919.2					
16	2005-06-10	14	25.27	258.9					
17	2006-04-16	67	34.69	1227.5					
18	2007-03-27	89	27.88	1735					
19	2008-04-23	81	36.52	1573.4					
20	2009-03-29	67	35.84	1484.9					
21	2009-07-02	10	21.04	169.6					
22	2010-04-12	58	39.74	1367.4					
23	2010-06-28	13	21.69	228.9					
24	2011-04-13	64	36.05	1485.9					
25	2012-04-06	57	38.71	1192					
26	2012-06-10	14	25.64	245.6					
27	2012-06-30	12	23.01	224.7					
28	2013-04-17	31	33.19	732					
29	2013-06-03	22	27.61	343.4					
30	2014-03-26	43	30.08	884.6					
31	2014-05-14	17	28.66	309.8					
32	2014-06-29	14	21.4	213.4					
33	2015-04-11	13	28.01	268.6					
34	2015-05-09	17	25.39	276.2					
35	2015-06-29	8	22.65	155.5					
36	2016-03-17	10	21.08	166.7					
37	2016-05-02	62	27.2	1053.2					
38	2017-03-24	12	19.24	204.2					
39	2017-04-15	11	28.98	226.8					
40	2017-05-04	20	24.98	357.2					
41	2017-06-11	7	18.63	108.9					
42	2018-04-12	52	29.84	967.1					
43	2018-06-14	8	15.77	115.5					